

Probabilistic Refinement Session Types

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1 SYNTAX

1.1 Types

The PRest language integrates refinement session types [2] and probabilistic resource-aware session types [4]. The syntax of PRest's types are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
A, B, C & ::= \oplus\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L} \mid \&\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L} \\
& \mid A \otimes B \mid A \multimap B \\
& \mid ?\{\phi\}.A \mid !\{\phi\}.A \\
& \mid \exists r.A \mid \forall r.A \mid \triangleright^w A \mid \triangleleft^w A \\
& \mid \oplus_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_l} : A_l\}_{l \in L} \mid \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_l} : A_l\}_{l \in L} \\
& \mid X[\bar{e}] \mid \mathbf{1}
\end{aligned}$$

PRest follows the tradition of intuitionistic session types [1]. Types are assigned dual meaning depending on whether they are used in a *left-rule* or a *right-rule*. Note that $X[\bar{e}]$ is a type name X applied to refinement expressions \bar{e} . All types in PRest are implicitly *equi-recursive*; type names are equal to their definitions and do not need explicit folding and unfolding. So the meaning of $X[\bar{e}]$ is determined by the definition of X .

Syntax	Left-meaning	Right-meaning
$\oplus\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L}$	Receive a label in L , continue as A_l .	Send a label in L , continue as A_l .
$\&\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L}$	Send a label in L , continue as A_l .	Receive a label in L , continue as A_l .
$A \otimes B$	Receive a channel of type A , continue as B .	Send a channel of type A , continue as B .
$A \multimap B$	Send a channel of type A , continue as B .	Receive a channel of type A , continue as B .
$?\{\phi\}.A$	Receive a proof of proposition ϕ , continue as A .	Send a proof of proposition ϕ , continue as A .
$!\{\phi\}.A$	Send a proof of proposition ϕ , continue as A .	Receive a proof of proposition ϕ , continue as A .
$\exists r.A$	Receive some expression e , continue as $A[e/r]$.	Send some expression e , continue as $A[e/r]$.
$\forall r.A$	Send some expression e , continue as $A[e/r]$.	Receive some expression e , continue as $A[e/r]$.
$\triangleright^w A$	Receive w units of potential, continue as A .	Send w units of potential, continue as A .
$\triangleleft^w A$	Send w units of potential, continue as A .	Receive w units of potential, continue as A .
$\oplus_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_l} : A_l\}_{l \in L}$	Receive a probabilistic label in L , continue as A_l .	Send a probabilistic label in L , continue as A_l .
$\&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_l} : A_l\}_{l \in L}$	Send a probabilistic label in L , continue as A_l .	Receive a probabilistic label in L , continue as A_l .
$\mathbf{1}$	Wait for channel to close	Close channel

1.2 Refinement Expressions

Types in PRest may contain *refinement expressions*. These are arithmetic expressions used for describing the states of programs. They have the following syntax:

$$\begin{aligned}
e, p, w & ::= v \mid e + e \mid e - e \mid e \times e \mid e \div e \mid r \\
v & ::= \text{real-constant}
\end{aligned}$$

The r here is a refinement variable. p will be used in contexts referring to probability expressions and w will be used in contexts referring to resource expressions.

1.3 Refinement Propositions

The range of refinement expressions can be constrained using logical propositions. The syntax of propositions are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi & ::= e = e \mid e < e \mid \top \mid \perp \\
& \mid \phi \wedge \phi \mid \phi \vee \phi \mid \neg\phi \mid \exists r.\phi \mid \forall r.\phi
\end{aligned}$$

We may use other operators such as \leq, \geq , etc. as they can be encoded using the above syntax.

1.4 Process Terms

Processes in PReST take the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
P, Q ::= & x.k ; P \mid \text{case } x (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} \mid \text{send } x y ; P \mid x \leftarrow \text{recv } y ; P \\
& \mid \text{assert } x \{\phi\} ; P \mid \text{assume } x \{\phi\} ; P \mid \text{send } x [e] ; P \mid [x] \leftarrow \text{recv } y ; P \\
& \mid x.k ; P \mid \text{pcase } x (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} \mid \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P \mid T \Rightarrow Q) \\
& \mid \text{work } w ; P \mid \text{pay } x w ; P \mid \text{get } x w ; P \\
& \mid x \leftarrow f [\bar{e}] \bar{y} ; P \mid \text{close } x \mid \text{wait } x ; P \mid x \leftrightarrow y
\end{aligned}$$

Intuitively, these constructs perform the following operations:

Syntax	Meaning
$x.k ; P$	Send a label k on channel x , continue executing process P .
$\text{case } x (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}$	Receive a label on x , perform case analysis and enter associated branch P_k .
$\text{send } x y ; P$	Send channel y on channel x , continue executing process P .
$x \leftarrow \text{recv } y ; P$	Receive a channel on y , bind it to x and continue executing process P .
$\text{assert } x \{\phi\} ; P$	Prove proposition ϕ and send the proof on x , continue executing process P .
$\text{assume } x \{\phi\} ; P$	Receive a proof of ϕ on channel x , continue executing process P .
$\text{send } x [e] ; P$	Send refinement expression e on channel x , continue executing process P .
$[x] \leftarrow \text{recv } y ; P$	Receive refinement expression on y , bind it to x and continue executing process P .
$x.k ; P$	Send a probabilistic label k on channel x , continue executing process P .
$\text{pcase } x (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}$	Receive a probabilistic label on x , perform case analysis and enter associated branch P_k .
$\text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P \mid T \Rightarrow Q)$	Flip a coin with probability p of landing on heads. Execute P if landed on heads. Otherwise, execute Q .
$\text{work } w ; P$	Consume w units of potential to perform work, continue executing process P .
$\text{pay } x w ; P$	Send w units of potential on channel x , continue executing process P .
$\text{get } x w ; P$	Receive w units of potential on x , continue executing process P .
$x \leftarrow f [\bar{e}] \bar{y} ; P$	Spawn a new process f , using refinement expressions \bar{e} and channels \bar{y} as arguments. The provided channel of the newly spawned process is bound to x .
$\text{close } x$	Continue executing process P . Close channel x
$\text{wait } x ; P$	Wait for channel x to close, continue executing process P .
$x \leftrightarrow y$	Forward the communication taking place on y to x .

1.5 Process Configurations

The syntax of PReST configurations are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{E} & ::= (w, P) \mid \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \\
\mathcal{O} & ::= \text{proc}(c, \mathcal{E}) \\
\mathcal{C} & ::= \mathcal{O}_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \mathcal{O}_n
\end{aligned}$$

A configuration \mathcal{C} is a series of *semantic objects* \mathcal{C} in parallel composition.

Semantic objects can take two forms.

- (1) $\text{proc}(c, w, P)$: A single process P that provides channel c and has *work-counter* w .
- (2) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$: A nested distribution of configurations C_i that provide channel c with likelihood p_i .

We will use \mathcal{D} to refer to configurations that do not possess objects of form (2).

$$\mathcal{D} ::= \text{proc}(c_1, w_1, P_1) \parallel \dots \parallel \text{proc}(c_n, w_n, P_n)$$

2 VALIDITY

2.1 Signature Validity

In PReST, named types and named processes are defined in a global signature Σ . All of these definitions are required to be valid. The following rules $\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma'$ *valid* and \vdash_{Σ} *signature* are defined mutually recursively with the type validity judgment $V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A$ *valid* and process typing judgment $V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$.

$$\frac{\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma \text{ valid}}{\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma \text{ signature}} \quad \frac{}{\vdash_{\Sigma} (\cdot) \text{ valid}} \quad \frac{\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma' \text{ valid} \quad \bar{r} ; \phi \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid} \quad A \neq V'[\bar{e}]}{\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma', V[\bar{r} \mid \phi] = A \text{ valid}}_{\Sigma T} \quad \frac{\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma' \text{ valid} \quad \bar{r} ; \phi ; \Delta \vdash_{\Sigma}^w P :: (x : A) \quad \bar{r} ; \phi \neq 0 \leq w}{\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma', f[\bar{r} \mid \phi] \Delta =^w P :: (x : A) \text{ valid}}_{\Sigma P}$$

Intuitively, the judgment $\vdash_{\Sigma} \Sigma'$ *valid* states that Σ' is a valid signature under the assumption that Σ is a valid signature. The judgement \vdash_{Σ} *signature* states that Σ is a valid signature under the assumption that Σ itself is a valid signature. This definition of signature validity subsumes recursive types and recursive processes since types and processes can refer to themselves through Σ . All types in PReST are implicitly *equi-recursive*; type names are equal to their definitions and do not need explicit folding and unfolding.

2.2 Type Validity

The presence of refinements and probabilities in PReST types necessitates type validity checking. For instance, rule $\oplus V$ requires the probabilities of a probabilistic choice type to always sum up to 1.

$$\frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A_l \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \oplus \{l : A_l\}_{l \in L} \text{ valid}}_{\oplus V} \quad \frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A_l \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \& \{l : A_l\}_{l \in L} \text{ valid}}_{\& V} \quad \frac{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid} \quad V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} B \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \otimes B \text{ valid}}_{\otimes V}$$

$$\frac{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid} \quad V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} B \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \multimap B \text{ valid}}_{\multimap V} \quad \frac{X[\bar{r} \mid \phi] = A \in \Sigma \quad V ; C \neq \phi[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} X[\bar{e}] \text{ valid}}_V \quad \frac{}{V ; C \vdash 1 \text{ valid}}_1$$

$$\frac{V ; C \wedge \phi \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} ?\{\phi\}.A \text{ valid}}_{?V} \quad \frac{V ; C \wedge \phi \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} !\{\phi\}.A \text{ valid}}_{!V} \quad \frac{V, r ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \exists r.A \text{ valid}}_{\exists V} \quad \frac{V, r ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid}}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \forall r.A \text{ valid}}_{\forall V} \quad \frac{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid} \quad V ; C \neq 0 \leq w}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \triangleright^w A \text{ valid}}_{\triangleright V}$$

$$\frac{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A \text{ valid} \quad V ; C \neq 0 \leq w}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \triangleleft^w A \text{ valid}}_{\triangleleft V} \quad \frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A_l \text{ valid} \quad V ; C \neq 0 \leq p_l \leq 1 \quad V ; C \neq \sum_{l \in L} p_l = 1}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \oplus \{l^{p_l} : A_l\}_{l \in L} \text{ valid}}_{\oplus P V}$$

$$\frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A_l \text{ valid} \quad V ; C \neq 0 \leq p_l \leq 1 \quad V ; C \neq \sum_{l \in L} p_l = 1}{V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} \&_P \{l^{p_l} : A_l\}_{l \in L} \text{ valid}}_{\&_P V}$$

3 TYPING RULES

For all process typing judgments of the form $V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$, we implicitly require that A is a valid type according to the judgment $V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} A$ valid and for all $(y : B) \in \Delta$, type B is a valid type according to $V ; C \vdash_{\Sigma} B$ valid. The process typing rules of PRest are organized in 4 categories: basic rules, refinement rules, ergometric rules and probabilistic rules.

3.1 Basic Rules

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w_l} P_l :: (x : A_l) \quad V ; C \models w_l \leq w}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{case } x (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (x : \&\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L})} \&R \qquad \frac{(k \in L) \quad V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A_k) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \&\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^w (x.k ; Q) :: (z : C)} \&L \\
\\
\frac{(k \in L) \quad V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A_k)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w (x.k ; P) :: (x : \oplus\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L})} \oplus R \qquad \frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A_l) \vdash^w Q_l :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \oplus\{l : A_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^w \text{case } x (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (z : C)} \oplus L \\
\\
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P : (x : B)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (y : A) \vdash^w (\text{send } x \ y ; P) :: (x : A \otimes B)} \otimes R \qquad \frac{V ; C ; \Delta, (y : A), (x : B) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A \otimes B) \vdash^w (y \leftarrow \text{recv } x ; Q) :: (z : C)} \otimes L \\
\\
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta, (y : A) \vdash^w P :: (x : B)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w (y \leftarrow \text{recv } x ; P) :: (x : A \multimap B)} \multimap R \qquad \frac{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : B) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A \multimap B), (y : A) \vdash^w (\text{send } x \ y ; Q) :: (z : C)} \multimap L \qquad \frac{V ; C \models 0 \leq w}{V ; C ; \cdot \vdash^w (\text{close } x) :: (x : 1)} 1R \\
\\
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : 1) \vdash^w (\text{wait } x ; Q) :: (z : C)} 1L \qquad \frac{V ; C \models 0 \leq w}{V ; C ; y : A \vdash^w (x \leftrightarrow y) :: (x : A)} \text{id} \\
\\
\frac{f[\bar{r} \mid \phi] \overline{y'} : B =^{w_f} P :: (x' : A) \in \Sigma \quad V ; C ; \Delta', (x : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \vdash^{w-w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} Q :: (z : C)}{\Delta = (y : B[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \quad V ; C \models \phi[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \quad V ; C \models w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \leq w} \text{spawn} \\
V ; C ; \Delta, \Delta' \vdash^w (x \leftarrow f[\bar{e}] \bar{y} ; Q) :: (z : C)
\end{array}$$

3.2 Refinement Rules

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A[e/r])}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{send } x [e] ; P :: (x : \exists r.A)} \exists R \qquad \frac{V, r ; C ; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \exists r.A) \vdash^w [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } x ; Q :: (z : C)} \exists L \qquad \frac{V, r ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } x ; P :: (x : \forall r.A)} \forall R \\
\\
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A[e/r]) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \forall r.A) \vdash^w \text{send } x [e] ; Q :: (z : C)} \forall L \qquad \frac{V ; C \models \phi \quad V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{assert } x \{\phi\} ; P :: (x : \{?\phi\}.A)} ?R \\
\\
\frac{V ; C \wedge \phi ; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \{?\phi\}.A) \vdash^w \text{assume } x \{\phi\} ; Q :: (z : C)} ?L \qquad \frac{V ; C \wedge \phi ; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{assume } x \{\phi\} ; P :: (x : !\{\phi\}.A)} !R \\
\\
\frac{V ; C \models \phi \quad V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^w Q :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : !\{\phi\}.A) \vdash^w \text{assert } x \{\phi\} ; Q :: (z : C)} !L
\end{array}$$

3.3 Ergometric Rules

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w-w'} P :: (x : A) \quad V ; C \models w' \leq w}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{pay } x \ w' ; P :: (x : \triangleright^{w'} A)} \triangleright R \qquad \frac{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^{w+w'} P :: (z : C)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \triangleright^{w'} A) \vdash^w \text{get } x \ w' ; P :: (z : C)} \triangleright L \qquad \frac{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w+w'} P :: (x : A)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{get } x \ w' ; P :: (x : \triangleleft^{w'} A)} \triangleleft R \\
\\
\frac{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^{w-w'} P :: (z : C) \quad V ; C \models w' \leq w}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \triangleleft^{w'} A) \vdash^w \text{pay } x \ w' ; P :: (z : C)} \triangleleft L \qquad \frac{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w-w'} P :: (x : A) \quad V ; C \models 0 \leq w' \leq w}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^w \text{work } w' ; P :: (x : A)} \text{Work}
\end{array}$$

3.4 Probabilistic Rules

To define probabilistic rules, weighted sum operators $+^L$ and $+^R$ are introduced. They add together the probabilities of types in the context and provided channel. The following two cases are the only non-trivial cases.

$$p \cdot \&_P \{ \ell^{q_\ell} : A_\ell \}_{\ell \in L} +^L (1-p) \cdot \&_P \{ \ell^{r_\ell} : A_\ell \}_{\ell \in L} = \&_P \{ \ell^{p \cdot q_\ell + (1-p) \cdot r_\ell} : A_\ell \}_{\ell \in L}$$

$$p \cdot \oplus_P \{ \ell^{q_\ell} : A_\ell \}_{\ell \in L} +^R (1-p) \cdot \oplus_P \{ \ell^{r_\ell} : A_\ell \}_{\ell \in L} = \oplus_P \{ \ell^{p \cdot q_\ell + (1-p) \cdot r_\ell} : A_\ell \}_{\ell \in L}$$

All other cases reduce to identity.

$$\frac{\forall V, \exists \{ \Delta_H, \Delta_T, A_H, A_T, w_H, w_T \}, \quad \cdot ; C ; \Delta_H \vdash^{w_H} P_H :: (x : A_H) \quad \cdot ; C ; \Delta_T \vdash^{w_T} P_T :: (x : A_T) \quad \cdot ; C \models 0 \leq p \leq 1 \quad \cdot ; C \models 0 \leq w_H \quad \cdot ; C \models 0 \leq w_T \quad \cdot ; C \models \Delta = p \cdot \Delta_H +^L (1-p) \cdot \Delta_T \quad \cdot ; C \models A = p \cdot A_H +^R (1-p) \cdot A_T \quad \cdot ; C \models w = p \cdot w_H + (1-p) \cdot w_T}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w} \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T) :: (x : A)} \text{flip}$$

$$\frac{\forall V, \exists \{ \Delta_I, C_I, w_I \}_{I \in L}, \quad (\forall I \in L) \quad \cdot ; C ; \Delta_I, (x : A_I) \vdash^{w_I} Q_I :: (z : C_I) \quad \cdot ; C \models 0 \leq w_I \quad \cdot ; C \models \Delta = \sum_{I \in L}^L p_I \cdot \Delta_I \quad \cdot ; C \models C = \sum_{I \in L}^R p_I \cdot C_I \quad \cdot ; C \models w = \sum_{I \in L} p_I \cdot w_I}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \oplus_P \{ I^{p_I} : A_I \}_{I \in L}) \vdash^{w} \text{pcase } x (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (z : C)} \oplus_P L \quad \frac{(k \in L) \quad V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w} P :: (x : A_k) \quad V ; C \models p_k = 1 \quad V ; C \models p_j = 0 \quad (j \neq k)}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w} x..k ; P :: (x : \oplus_P \{ I^{p_I} : A_I \}_{I \in L})} \oplus_P R$$

$$\frac{(k \in L) \quad V ; C ; \Delta, (x : A_k) \vdash^{w} P :: (z : C) \quad V ; C \models p_k = 1 \quad V ; C \models p_j = 0 \quad (j \neq k)}{V ; C ; \Delta, (x : \&_P \{ I^{p_I} : A_I \}_{I \in L}) \vdash^{w} x..k ; P :: (z : C)} \&_P L \quad \frac{\forall V, \exists \{ \Delta_I, w_I \}_{I \in L}, \quad (\forall I \in L) \quad \cdot ; C ; \Delta_I \vdash^{w_I} Q_I :: (x : A_I) \quad \cdot ; C \models \Delta = \sum_{I \in L}^L p_I \cdot \Delta_I \quad \cdot ; C \models w = \sum_{I \in L} p_I \cdot w_I}{V ; C ; \Delta \vdash^{w} \text{pcase } x (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (x : \&_P \{ I^{p_I} : A_I \}_{I \in L})} \&_P R$$

3.5 Configuration Rules

The typing rules of processes are lifted to configurations. Since configurations represent the state of processes at runtime, the typing of singleton processes (rule T:PROC) is required to be *refinement-closed*, i.e. $V = \cdot$ and $C = \top$.

$$\frac{\cdot ; T ; \Delta \vdash^{w'} P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; T \models 0 \leq w}{\Delta \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, P) :: (c : A)} \text{T:PROC} \quad \frac{(\forall i \in I) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; T \models \Delta = \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i \quad \cdot ; T \models A = \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; T \models w = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i}{\Delta \Vdash^{w} \text{proc}(c, \{ C_i : p_i \}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)} \text{T:DIST}$$

$$\frac{\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C :: (\Delta, \Delta')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C) :: (\Delta, (c : A))} \text{T:COMPOSE}$$

4 STATUS JUDGMENTS

The facilitate the proof of progress (Section 8), a series of judgments are defined which characterize the status of evaluation. Some of these judgments utilize a *sort* $\kappa \in \{\top, \text{det}, \oplus_p, \&_p\}$ for categorizing communication.

- det : Communication on a non-probabilistic channel.
- \oplus_p : Probabilistic communication on a \oplus_p channel.
- $\&_p$: Probabilistic communication on a $\&_p$ channel.

Sort \top is the super-sort of all sorts ($\kappa <: \top$).

The $\text{FV}^R(\cdot)$ and $\text{FV}^L(\cdot)$ functions partition the channels occurring in a configuration C into two sets: $\text{FV}^R(C)$ are the channels provided by C and $\text{FV}^L(\cdot)$ are those that are used by C .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FV}^R(\text{proc}(c, w, P)) &:= \{c\} & \text{FV}^L(\text{proc}(c, w, P)) &:= \text{FV}(P) \setminus \{c\} \\ \text{FV}^R(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})) &:= \bigcup_{i \in I} \text{FV}^R(C_i) & \text{FV}^L(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})) &:= \bigcup_{i \in I} \text{FV}^L(C_i) \\ \text{FV}^R(O \parallel C) &:= (\text{FV}^R(O) \cup \text{FV}^R(C)) \setminus \text{FV}^L(O) & \text{FV}^L(O \parallel C) &:= (\text{FV}^L(O) \cup \text{FV}^L(C)) \setminus \text{FV}^R(C) \end{aligned}$$

4.1 Live

A configuration is live if one of its processes is ready to make a transition that does not involve communication. Constructs that induce such transitions include flip, spawn, and work. A concrete example of a live configuration:

$$C \triangleq \text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H | \top \Rightarrow P_T))$$

The process in this configuration is ready to make a flip transition without communicating with others.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H | \top \Rightarrow P_T)) \text{ live}} \text{L:FLIP} & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow f[\bar{e}] \bar{y}; Q) \text{ live}} \text{L:DEF} & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{work } w'; P) \text{ live}} \text{L:WORK} \\ \frac{C_{i_0} \text{ live}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \text{ live}} \text{L:DIST} & \frac{O \text{ live}}{(O \parallel C) \text{ live}} \text{L:COMPOSE:H} & \frac{C \text{ live}}{(O \parallel C) \text{ live}} \text{L:COMPOSE:T} \end{array}$$

4.2 Poised

Poised denotes configurations whose processes are all ready for communication with an external client. This is equivalent, in principle, to a configuration that is waiting for I/O from an external user. There are no internal transitions possible anymore and communication with an external client outside of the configuration is the only possibility. Communication with this external client will then drive internal transitions. A concrete example of a poised configuration:

$$C \triangleq \text{proc}(c, w, c.\text{Ack}; P)$$

The process in this configuration is poised to send an Ack label on c to an external client. After an external process receives Ack (synchronously), the process transitions to $\text{proc}(c, w, P)$ and can begin evaluating P .

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, c.k; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\oplus & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{case } c (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\& & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{send } c \ x; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\otimes \\ \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow \text{recv } c; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\rightarrow & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{assert } c \ \{\phi\}; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\? & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{assume } c \ \{\phi\}; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\! \\ \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{send } c [e]; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\exists & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, [c] \leftarrow \text{recv } e; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\forall & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{pay } c \ w'; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\triangleright \\ \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{get } c \ w'; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\triangleleft & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, c.k; P) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\oplus_p & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{pcase } c (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\&_p & \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{close } c) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\mathbf{1} \\ \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, c \rightarrow x) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\text{ID} & \frac{(\forall i \in I) \ C_i \text{ poised}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\text{DIST} & \frac{O \text{ poised} \quad C \text{ poised}}{(O \parallel C) \text{ poised}} \text{P:}\text{COMPOSE} \end{array}$$

4.3 (d, κ) -Poised

The $C(c, \kappa)$ -poised judgment is similar to C poised as they both describe some configuration C blocked on the channels it provides. However, unlike C poised which requires *all* processes in C to be blocked, $C(c, \kappa)$ -poised requires only one process to be blocked. Moreover, C can be unblocked by performing a κ sorted communication.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, c.k ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\oplus \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{case } c (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\& \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{send } c \ x ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\otimes \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow \text{recv } c ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\neg\circ \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{assert } c \ \{\phi\} ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\? \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{assume } c \ \{\phi\} ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\! \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{send } c \ [e] ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\exists \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, [c] \leftarrow \text{recv } e ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\forall \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{pay } c \ w' ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\triangleright \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{get } c \ w' ; P) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\triangleleft \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, c.k ; P) (c, \oplus_P)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\oplus_P \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{pcase } c (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) (c, \&_P)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\&_P \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{close } c) (c, \text{det})\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\mathbf{1} \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, c \leftrightarrow x) (c, \top)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\text{ID} \quad \frac{C_{i_0} (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\text{DIST} \\
\frac{O (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\text{COMPOSE:H} \quad \frac{C (d, \kappa)\text{-poised} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^L(O)}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:}\text{COMPOSE:T}
\end{array}$$

4.4 (d, κ) -Blocked

The (d, κ) -blocked judgment is similar to (c, κ) -poised. But instead being blocked on a provided channel, it is blocked on used channel.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{case } c (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\oplus \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, c.k ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\& \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{send } c \ y ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\neg\circ \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, y \leftarrow \text{recv } c ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\otimes \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{assert } c \ \{\phi\} ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\! \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{assume } c \ \{\phi\} ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\? \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{send } c \ [e] ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\forall \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, [y] \leftarrow \text{recv } c ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\exists \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{get } c \ w' ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\triangleright \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{pay } c \ w' ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\triangleleft \\
\frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{pcase } c (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) (c, \oplus_P)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\oplus_P \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, c.k ; Q) (c, \&_P)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\&_P \quad \frac{}{\text{proc}(d, w, \text{wait } c ; Q) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\mathbf{1} \\
\frac{C_{i_0} (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}}{\text{proc}(e, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\text{DIST} \quad \frac{O (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^R(C)}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\text{COMPOSE:H} \quad \frac{C (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\text{COMPOSE:T}
\end{array}$$

4.5 (d, κ) -Comm

In $C(d, \kappa)$ -comm, two processes in the configuration are ready to communicate on channel d . The “sort” of communication is identified by κ . A concrete example of a (d, det) -comm configuration:

$$C \triangleq \text{proc}(c, w_1, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_2, \text{send } d \ \text{msg} ; Q)$$

The first process $\text{proc}(c, w_1, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P)$ is providing a channel c , but it is blocked and waiting to receive from channel d . The second process $\text{proc}(d, w_2, \text{send } d \ \text{msg} ; Q)$ is poised to send a message along its provided channel d . The composition these two process creates a (d, det) -comm configuration as they are ready to communicate deterministically (indicated by $\kappa = \text{det}$) along channel d . Observe the CM:COMPOSE:C rule which composes together (d, κ) -blocked and (d, κ') -poised configurations for communication.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{C_{i_0} (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}} \text{CM:}\text{DIST} \quad \frac{O (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}} \text{CM:}\text{COMPOSE:H} \quad \frac{C (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}} \text{CM:}\text{COMPOSE:T} \\
\frac{O (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked} \quad C (d, \kappa')\text{-poised} \quad \kappa <: \kappa'}{(O \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}} \text{CM:}\text{COMPOSE:C}
\end{array}$$

5 NESTED MULTIVERSE SEMANTICS

PrEST utilizes nested multiverse semantics [4] to prove preservation (Section 7) and progress (Section 8).

5.1 Single Process Rules

- (E:DEF) $\text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow f[\bar{e}] \bar{d}; Q) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, w, Q[b/x]) \parallel \text{proc}(b, 0, P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}'])$
 for $f[\bar{r} \mid \phi] \bar{y}' : \bar{B} =^{w'} P :: (x' : A) \in \Sigma$
- (E:WORK) $\text{proc}(c, w, \text{work } w'; P) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, w + w', P)$
- (E:FLIP) $\text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{\text{proc}(c, w, P_H) : p, \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) : 1 - p\})$
- (E:DIST) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\})$
 for some $i_0 \in I$ such that $C_{i_0} \mapsto C'_{i_0}$

5.2 Communication Rules

- (C:⊕) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d.k; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:&) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, d.k; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k)$
- (C:⊗) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d x; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[x/y]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:→) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d x; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[x/y])$
- (C:?) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assume } d \{\phi\}; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assert } d \{\phi'\}; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:!) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assert } d \{\phi\}; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assume } d \{\phi'\}; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:∃) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d [e]; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[e/r]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:∀) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d [e]; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[e/r])$
- (C:1) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{wait } d; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{close } d) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q)$
- (C:ID) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, Q\langle d \rangle) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d \leftrightarrow x) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q\langle d \rangle[x/d])$
 for $Q\langle d \rangle$ (d, κ)-blocked
- (C:▷) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{get } d w; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pay } d w; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:◁) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pay } d w; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{get } d w; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:⊕P) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d..k; P) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus p} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (C:&P) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, d..k; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \xrightarrow{d, \& p} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k)$
- (C:DIST) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\})$
 for some $i_0 \in I$ such that $C_{i_0} \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'_{i_0}$
- (C:SDIST:R) $\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$
 for $\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$
- (C:SDIST:L) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$
 for $\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$
- (C:BDIST:D) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in J}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} C''$
 for $\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel C'_j) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in I, j \in J}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} C''$
- (C:BDIST:R) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in J}) \xrightarrow{d, \& p} C''$
 for $\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel C'_j) : p'_j\}_{j \in J}) \xrightarrow{d, \& p} C''$
- (C:BDIST:L) $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in J}) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus p} C''$
 for $\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in J})) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus p} C''$

6 DISTRIBUTION-BASED SEMANTICS

A non-nested, distribution-based semantics is also defined for PREST. Flattening and simulation (Section 9) allows the two semantics to be connected. It is more convenient to prove theorems about cost analysis (Section 10) using the distribution-based semantics.

- (S:⊕) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d.k ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:&) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, d.k ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k)$
- (S:⊗) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d x ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[x/y]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:→) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d x ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[x/y])$
- (S:?) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assume } d \{\phi\} ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assert } d \{\phi'\} ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:!) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assume } d \{\phi'\} ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:∃) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d [e] ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[e/r]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:∀) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d [e] ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[e/r])$
- (S:1) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{wait } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{close } d) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q)$
- (S:ID) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, Q\langle d \rangle) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d \leftrightarrow x) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q\langle d \rangle[x/d])$
- (S:⊃) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{get } d w ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pay } d w ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:⊃) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pay } d w ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{get } d w ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:⊕p) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d..k ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$
- (S:&p) $\text{proc}(c, w_c, d..k ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k)$
- (S:DEF) $\text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow f [\bar{e}] \bar{d} ; Q) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q[b/x]) \parallel \text{proc}(b, 0, P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}'])$
for $f [\bar{r} \mid \phi] \bar{y}' : \bar{B} = w' P :: (x' : A) \in \Sigma$
- (S:WORK) $\text{proc}(c, w, \text{work } w' ; P) \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w + w', P)$

$$(SP:DET) \quad \mathcal{D} \xrightarrow{\text{prob}} \{\mathcal{D}' : 1\} \quad \text{for } \mathcal{D} \xrightarrow{\text{det}} \mathcal{D}'$$

$$(SP:FLIP) \quad \text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) \xrightarrow{\text{prob}} \{\text{proc}(c, w, P_H) : p, \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) : (1 - p)\}$$

Lift the configuration-to-distribution relation $\xrightarrow{\text{prob}}$ to distribution-to-distribution relation \Rightarrow .

$$\frac{\mu = \{\mathcal{D}_i : p_i\}_{i \in I} \quad \exists i_0 \in I : \mathcal{D}_{i_0} \xrightarrow{\text{prob}} \mu'_{i_0}}{\mu \Rightarrow \{\mathcal{D}_i : p_i\}_{i \in I / \{i_0\}} + p_{i_0} \cdot \mu'_{i_0}} \qquad \frac{\mu = \{\mathcal{D}_i : p_i\}_{i \in I} \quad \forall i \in I : \mathcal{D}_i \text{ poised}}{\mu \Rightarrow \mu}$$

7 PRESERVATION

The type preservation for PReST is proven using the nested multiverse semantics (Section 5). The nested structure of distributions allow effects of probabilistic branching to be localized.

PROPOSITION 7.1. *The substitutions below are type-preserving and thus admissible.*

- (1) *If $V; C; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$, then for any fresh y , it holds that $V; C; \Delta \vdash^w P[y/x] :: (y : A)$.*
- (2) *If $V; C; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^w P :: (z : C)$, then for any fresh y , it holds that $V; C; \Delta, (y : A) \vdash^w P[y/x] :: (z : C)$.*
- (3) *If $V, r; C; \Delta, (x : A) \vdash^w P :: (z : C)$, then for any closed v , it holds that $V, C[v/r], \Delta[v/r] \vdash^{w[v/r]} P[v/r] :: (z : C[v/r])$.*

PROPOSITION 7.2. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w (C_1 \parallel \text{proc}(c, \mathcal{E}_c \langle d \rangle) \parallel C_2 \parallel \text{proc}(d, \mathcal{E}_d) \parallel C_3) :: \Gamma$, then $\Delta \Vdash^w (C_1 \parallel \text{proc}(c, \mathcal{E}_c \langle d \rangle) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \mathcal{E}_d) \parallel C_2 \parallel C_3) :: \Gamma$.*

PROPOSITION 7.3. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w (C_1 \parallel C_2 \parallel C_3) :: \Gamma$, then there exists Δ', Γ', w' such that $\Delta' \Vdash^{w'} C_2 :: \Gamma'$.*

PROPOSITION 7.4. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w (C_1 \parallel C_2 \parallel C_3) :: \Gamma$ and $\Delta' \Vdash^{w'} C_2 :: \Gamma'$, then for any C'_2 such that $\Delta' \Vdash^{w'} C'_2 :: \Gamma'$ it holds that $\Delta \Vdash^w (C_1 \parallel C'_2 \parallel C_3) :: \Gamma$.*

PROPOSITION 7.5. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then for all $c \in \text{dom}(\Gamma)$, there exists exactly one process $\text{proc}(c, \mathcal{E})$ which provides channel c in C .*

LEMMA 7.6. *If $\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} C_1 :: \Gamma$ and $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C_2 :: (\Delta, \Delta')$, then $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1 + w_2} (C_1 \parallel C_2) :: (\Delta, \Gamma)$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} C_1 :: \Gamma$. □

LEMMA 7.7. *If $V; C; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$, then for all C' such that $V; C' \vDash C$ there is $V; C'; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $V; C; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$ and transitivity of $V; C' \vDash C$. □

LEMMA 7.8. *If $V; C; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$, then for all w' such that $V; C \vDash w \leq w'$ there is $V; C; \Delta \vdash^{w'} P :: (x : A)$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $V; C; \Delta \vdash^w P :: (x : A)$ □

LEMMA 7.9. *If there is $\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$ and $\Delta_1, (d : \oplus_P \{ \dots \}) \Vdash^{w_c} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A)$ and $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_d} C :: (d : \oplus_P \{ \dots \})$, then Q must be of the form $\text{pcase } d \ (.. \Rightarrow ..)$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. Out of the non-DIST rules, only C:ID and C: \oplus_P are compatible with the typing judgment $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_d} C :: (d : \oplus_P \{ \dots \})$. Case C: \oplus_P is trivial.

For case C:ID we have $Q \langle r \rangle \ (d, \kappa)$ -blocked. Only BL: \oplus_P is compatible with the typing judgment $\Delta_1, (d : \oplus_P \{ \dots \}) \Vdash^{w_c} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A)$. This shows that Q is of the form $\text{pcase } d \ (.. \Rightarrow ..)$.

Out of the DIST rules, only C:DIST:R is applicable. So we have

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'}{\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'}$$

such that $C = \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})$.

Notice that C:DIST is the only rule that can derive $\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. So there exists $i_0 \in I$ such that $\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_{i_0} \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'_0$. Inversion on $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_d} \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (d : \oplus_P \{ \dots \})$ gives $\Delta_2, i_0 \Vdash^{w_0} C_{i_0} :: (d : \oplus_P \{ \dots \})$. The induction hyp. concludes that Q is of the form $\text{pcase } d \ (.. \Rightarrow ..)$. □

LEMMA 7.10. *If there is $C \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$ and $\Delta_1, (d : \&_P \{ \dots \}) \Vdash^{w_c} C :: (c : A)$ and $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_d} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : \&_P \{ \dots \})$ then P must be of the form $\text{pcase } d \ (.. \Rightarrow ..)$ or $d \leftrightarrow x$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $C \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. Out of the non-DIST rules, only C:ID and C: $\&_P$ are compatible with the typing judgment $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_d} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : \&_P \{ \dots \})$. The proof is trivial in both cases.

Of the DIST rules, only C:SDIST:L is applicable. So we have

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'}$$

such that $C = \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})$.

Notice that C:DIST is the only rule that can derive $\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. So there exists $i_0 \in I$ such that $C_{i_0} \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'_0$. Inversion on $\Delta_1, (d : \&_P \{ \dots \}) \Vdash^{w_c} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)$ gives $\Delta_1, i_0, (d : \&_P \{ \dots \}) \Vdash^{w_0} C_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0})$. The induction hyp. shows that P is of the form $\text{pcase } d \ (.. \Rightarrow ..)$ or $d \leftrightarrow x$. □

THEOREM 7.11 (PRESERVATION PART 1). *If $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$ and $C \mapsto C'$, then $\Delta \Vdash^w C' :: \Gamma$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $C \mapsto C'$. By Propositions 7.3 and 7.4, it suffices to consider the atomic rewriting rules.

Case (E:WORK):

$$\text{proc}(c, w, \text{work } w' ; P) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, w + w', P)$$

$\Delta \Vdash^{w+w''} \text{proc}(c, w, \text{work } w' ; P) :: \Gamma$ is well-typed. By inversion we have $\Gamma = (c : A)$ and

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w''} \text{work } w' ; P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w}{\Delta \Vdash^{w+w''} \text{proc}(c, w, \text{work } w' ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w''} \text{work } w' ; P :: (c : A)$ gives us

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w''-w'} P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w' \leq w''}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w''} \text{work } w' ; P :: (c : A)}$$

By T:PROC we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w''-w'} P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w + w'}{\Delta \Vdash^{w+w''} \text{proc}(c, w + w', P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (E:FLIP):

$$\text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{\text{proc}(c, w, P_H) : p, \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) : 1 - p\})$$

$\Delta \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) :: \Gamma$ is well-typed. By inversion we have $\Gamma = (c : A)$ and

$$\frac{\exists \{\Delta_H, \Delta_T, A_H, A_T, w_H, w_T\}, \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_H \vdash^{w_H} P_H :: (c : A_H) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_T \vdash^{w_T} P_T :: (c : A_T) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq p \leq 1 \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w}{\cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta = p \cdot \Delta_H +^L (1 - p) \cdot \Delta_T \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = p \cdot A_H +^R (1 - p) \cdot A_T \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w' = p \cdot w_H + (1 - p) \cdot w_T}{\Delta \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) :: (c : A)}$$

By T:PROC we have $\Delta_H \Vdash^{w+w_H} \text{proc}(c, w, P_H) :: (c : A_H)$ and $\Delta_T \Vdash^{w+w_T} \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) :: (c : A_T)$. Applying T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta = p \cdot \Delta_H +^L (1 - p) \cdot \Delta_T \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = p \cdot A_H +^R (1 - p) \cdot A_T \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w + w' = p \cdot (w + w_H) + (1 - p) \cdot (w + w_T) \quad \Delta_H \Vdash^{w+w_H} \text{proc}(c, w, P_H) :: (c : A_H) \quad \Delta_T \Vdash^{w+w_T} \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) :: (c : A_T)}{\Delta \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, \{\text{proc}(c, w, P_H) : p, \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) : 1 - p\}) :: (c : A)} \text{T:COMPOSE}$$

Case (E:DIST):

$$\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\}) \text{ where } i_0 \in I \text{ and } C_{i_0} \mapsto C'_{i_0}$$

$\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: \Gamma$ is well-typed. By inversion we have $\Gamma = (c : A)$ and

$$\frac{(\forall i \in I) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i = \Delta \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i = A \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i = w}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)}$$

Given $i_0 \in I$, we have $\Delta_{i_0} \Vdash^{w_{i_0}} C_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0})$. Applying the induction hypothesis gives us $\Delta_{i_0} \Vdash^{w_{i_0}} C'_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0})$. The weighted sums remain unchanged after reduction. So we may apply T:DIST to obtain

$$\frac{(\forall i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \Delta_{i_0} \Vdash^{w_{i_0}} C'_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0}) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i = \Delta \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i = A \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i = w}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\}) :: (c : A)} \text{T:DIST}$$

Case (E:DEF):

$$\text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow f [\bar{e}] \bar{d} ; Q) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, w, Q[b/x]) \parallel \text{proc}(b, 0, P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}']) \text{ where } f [\bar{r} \mid \phi] \bar{y}' : B =^{w_f} P :: (x' : A) \in \Sigma$$

$\Delta \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow f [\bar{e}] \bar{d} ; Q) :: \Gamma$ is well-typed. By inversion we have $\Gamma = (c : C)$ and $\Delta = \Delta_1, \Delta_2$ and

$$\frac{f [\bar{r} \mid \phi] \bar{y}' : B =^{w_f} P :: (x' : A) \in \Sigma \quad \Delta_1 = \bar{d} : B[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \phi[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2, (x : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \vdash^{w'-w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} Q :: (c : C) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \leq w'}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, x \leftarrow f [\bar{e}] \bar{d} ; Q) :: (c : C)}$$

From $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2, (x : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \vdash^{w'-w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} Q :: (c : C)$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2, (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \vdash^{w'-w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} Q[b/x] :: (c : C)$ by (1) of Proposition 7.1.

From $f[\bar{r} \mid \phi] \bar{y}' : B =^{w_f} P :: (x' : A) \in \Sigma$ we know that $\bar{r} ; \phi ; \bar{y}' : B \vdash^{w_f} P :: (x' : A)$ holds. Substituting \bar{r} for \bar{e} gives us $\cdot ; \phi[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] ; \bar{y}' : B[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \vdash^{w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] :: (x' : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}])$ by (3) of Proposition 7.1. Applying (1) and (2) of Proposition 7.1 gives us $\cdot ; \phi[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] ; \bar{d} : B[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \vdash^{w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}'] :: (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}])$. Applying Lemma 7.7 with $\cdot ; \top \vDash \phi[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]$ gives us $\cdot ; \top ; \bar{d} : B[\bar{e}/\bar{r}] \vdash^{w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}'] :: (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}])$.

By T:PROC we have $\Delta_2, (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \Vdash^{w+w'-w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} \text{proc}(c, w, Q[b/x]) :: (c : C)$ and $\Delta_1 \Vdash^{w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} \text{proc}(b, 0, P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}']) :: (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}])$. Applying T:DIST gives

$$\frac{\Delta_2, (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]) \Vdash^{w+w'-w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} \text{proc}(c, w, Q[b/x]) :: (c : C) \quad \Delta_1 \Vdash^{w_f[\bar{e}/\bar{r}]} \text{proc}(b, 0, P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}']) :: (b : A[\bar{e}/\bar{r}])}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, Q[b/x]) \parallel \text{proc}(b, 0, P[\bar{e}/\bar{r}, b/x', \bar{d}/\bar{y}']) :: (c : C)} \text{T:DIST}$$

□

THEOREM 7.12 (PRESERVATION PART 2). *If $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$ and $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$, then $\Delta \Vdash^w C' :: \Gamma$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. By Propositions 7.2 to 7.5 it suffices to consider the atomic rewriting rules.

Case (C:⊕):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d.k ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion of the typing judgment we have the following

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d.k ; P :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d.k ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B_l) \vdash^{w_l} Q_l :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_l \leq w_1}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \oplus\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_1} \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = \oplus\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L}$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d.k ; P :: (d : \oplus\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L})$ gives

$$\frac{(k \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : B_k)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d.k ; P :: (d : \oplus\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

For $k \in L$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B_k) \vdash^{w_k} Q_k :: (c : A)$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash w_k \leq w_1$. Applying Lemma 7.8 gives us $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B_k) \vdash^{w_1} Q_k :: (c : A)$. Now T:PROC and T:COMPOSE give us

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B_k) \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : B_k)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:&):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, d.k ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} d.k ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, d.k ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (d : B)$ gives

$$\frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_l} P_l :: (d : B_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_l \leq w_2}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{case } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (d : \&\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

such that $B = \&\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L}$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \&\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_1} d.k ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{(k \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B_k) \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \&\{l : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_1} d.k ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

For $k \in L$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_k} P_k :: (d : B_k)$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash w_k \leq w_2$. Applying Lemma 7.8 gives us $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P_k :: (d : B_k)$. T:PROC and T:COMPOSE give us

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B_k) \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k) :: (d : B_k)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:⊗):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d x ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[x/y]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{send } d x ; P :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d x ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{send } d x ; P :: (d : B)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta'_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : B')}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta'_2, (x : A') \vdash^{w_2} \text{send } d x ; P :: (d : A' \otimes B')}$$

such that $B = A' \otimes B'$ and $\Delta_2 = \Delta'_2, (x : A')$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A' \otimes B') \vdash^{w_1} y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (y : A'), (d : B') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A' \otimes B') \vdash^{w_1} y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

By (2) of Proposition 7.1 we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (x : A'), (d : B') \vdash^{w_1} Q[x/y] :: (c : A)$.

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (x : A'), (d : B') \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[x/y]) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta'_2 \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : B')}{\Delta_1, \Delta'_2, (x : A') \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[x/y]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:→):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d x ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[x/y])$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{send } d x ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d x ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{send } d x ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta'_1, (d : B') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta'_1, (x : A'), (d : A' \multimap B') \vdash^{w_1} \text{send } d x ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = A' \multimap B'$ and $\Delta_1 = \Delta'_1, (x : A')$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P :: (d : A' \multimap B')$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2, (y : A') \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : B')}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} y \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P :: (d : A' \multimap B')}$$

By (2) of Proposition 7.1 we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2, (x : A') \vdash^{w_2} P[x/y] :: (d : B')$.

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta'_1, (d : B') \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2, (x : A') \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[x/y]) :: (d : B')}{\Delta'_1, (x : A'), \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[x/y]) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:?):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assume } d \{ \phi \} ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assert } d \{ \phi' \} ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{assume } d \{\phi\} ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{assert } d \{\phi'\} ; P :: (d : B) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d \end{array}}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assume } d \{\phi\} ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assert } d \{\phi'\} ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{assume } d \{\phi\} ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \phi ; \Delta_1, (d : A') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : ?\{\phi\}.A') \vdash^{w_1} \text{assume } d \{\phi\} ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = ?\{\phi\}.A'$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{assert } d \{\phi'\} ; P :: (d : ?\{\phi\}.A')$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top \vDash \phi \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A')}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; P :: (d : ?\{\phi\}.A')}$$

such that $\phi = \phi'$.

By Lemma 7.7, $\cdot ; \top \vDash \phi$ and $\cdot ; \phi ; \Delta_1, (d : A') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)$.

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : A') \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : A')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:!):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assume } d \{\phi'\} ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{assume } d \{\phi'\} ; P :: (d : B) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d \end{array}}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{assume } d \{\phi'\} ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top \vDash \phi \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : !\{\phi\}.A') \vdash^{w_1} \text{assert } d \{\phi\} ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = !\{\phi\}.A'$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{assume } d \{\phi'\} ; P :: (d : !\{\phi\}.A')$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \phi ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A')}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{assume } d \{\phi\} ; P :: (d : !\{\phi\}.A')}$$

such that $\phi = \phi'$.

By Lemma 7.7, $\cdot ; \top \vDash \phi$ and $\cdot ; \phi ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A')$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A')$.

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : A') \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : A')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:∃):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d [e] ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[e/r]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{send } d [e] ; P :: (d : B) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d \end{array}}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{send } d [e] ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{r ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \exists r.A') \vdash^{w_1} [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = \exists r.A'$. Note that r does not occur in Δ_1, A or w_1 .

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{send } d [e] ; P :: (d : \exists r.A')$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A'[e/r])}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{send } d [e] ; P :: (d : \exists r.A')}$$

From (3) of Proposition 7.1 and $r ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A') \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)$ we obtain $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A'[e/r]) \vdash^{w_1} Q[e/r] :: (c : A)$ since r does not occur in w_1 .

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : A'[e/r]) \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[e/r]) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : A'[e/r])}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q[e/r]) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:V):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d [e] ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[e/r])$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{send } d [e] ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{send } d [e] ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{send } d [e] ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : A'[e/r]) \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \forall r.A') \vdash^{w_1} \text{send } d [e] ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = \forall r.A'$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P :: (d : \forall r.A')$ gives

$$\frac{r ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A')}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} [r] \leftarrow \text{recv } d ; P :: (d : \forall r.A')}$$

such that r does not occur in Δ_2 or w_2 .

From (3) of Proposition 7.1 and $r ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : A')$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P[e/r] :: (d : A'[e/r])$.

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : A'[e/r]) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[e/r]) :: (d : A'[e/r])}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P[e/r]) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:▷):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{get } d w' ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pay } d w' ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \triangleright^{w'} B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{get } d w' ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{pay } d w' ; P :: (d : \triangleright^{w'} B) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{get } d w' ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pay } d w' ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \triangleright^{w'} B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{get } d w' ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1+w'} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \triangleright^{w'} B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{get } d w' ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{pay } d \ w' ; P :: (d : \triangleright^{w'} B)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2 - w'} P :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w' \leq w_2}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{pay } d \ w' ; P :: (d : \triangleright^{w'} B)}$$

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1 + w' + w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2 - w' + w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : B)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:◁):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pay } d \ w' ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{get } d \ w' ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \triangleleft^{w'} B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{pay } d \ w' ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{get } d \ w' ; P :: (d : \triangleleft^{w'} B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pay } d \ w' ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{get } d \ w' ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \triangleleft^{w'} B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{pay } d \ w' ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1 - w'} Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w' \leq w_1}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \triangleleft^{w'} B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{pay } d \ w' ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{get } d \ w' ; P :: (d : \triangleleft^{w'} B)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2 + w'} P :: (d : B)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{get } d \ w' ; P :: (d : \triangleleft^{w'} B)}$$

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1 - w' + w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2 + w' + w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : B)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:1):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{wait } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{close } d) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{wait } d ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{close } d :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{wait } d ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{close } d) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{wait } d ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1 \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : 1) \vdash^{w_1} \text{wait } d ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = 1$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{close } d :: (d : 1)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w_2}{\cdot ; \top ; \cdot \vdash^{w_2} \text{close } d :: (d : 1)}$$

such that $\Delta_2 = \cdot$.

By Lemma 7.8, $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1 \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A)$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w_2$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1 \vdash^{w_1 + w_2} Q :: (c : A)$. By T:PROC we have $\Delta_1 \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q) :: (c : A)$.

Case (C:ID):

$$\frac{Q\langle d \rangle \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-blocked}}{\text{proc}(c, w_c, Q\langle d \rangle) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d \leftrightarrow x) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q\langle d \rangle[x/d])}$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} Q \langle d \rangle :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d \leftrightarrow x :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \vDash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q \langle d \rangle) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d \leftrightarrow x) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d \leftrightarrow x :: (d : B)$ gives

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w_2}{\cdot ; \top ; (x : B) \vdash^{w_2} d \leftrightarrow x :: (d : B)}$$

such that $\Delta_2 = (x : B)$.

From Lemma 7.8, $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} Q \langle d \rangle :: (c : A)$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w_2$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1+w_2} Q \langle d \rangle :: (c : A)$. From (2) of Proposition 7.1 and $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1+w_2} Q \langle d \rangle :: (c : A)$ we have $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (x : B) \vdash^{w_1+w_2} Q \langle d \rangle [x/d] :: (c : A)$.

By T:PROC we have $\Delta_1, (x : B) \vDash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c + w_d, Q \langle d \rangle [x/d]) :: (c : A)$.

Case (C:⊕P):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d..k ; P) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus P} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d..k ; P :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \vDash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, d..k ; P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\exists \{\Delta_{1,l}, A_l, w_{1,l}\}_{l \in L}, \quad (\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{1,l}, (d : B_l) \vdash^{w_{1,l}} Q_l :: (c : A_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_1 = \sum_{l \in L}^L p_l \cdot \Delta_{1,l} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{l \in L}^R p_l \cdot A_l \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 = \sum_{l \in L} p_l \cdot w_{1,l}}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \oplus P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_1} \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L} :: (c : A)}$$

such that $B = \oplus P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L}$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d..k ; P :: (d : \oplus P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L})$ gives

$$\frac{(k \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : B_k) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash p_k = 1 \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash p_j = 0 \quad (j \neq k)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} d..k ; P :: (d : \oplus P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

From $\cdot ; \top \vDash p_k = 1$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash p_j = 0$ ($j \neq k$) we know that $\cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_1 = \Delta_{1,k}$, $\cdot ; \top \vDash A = A_k$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 = w_{1,k}$.

For $k \in L$ there are $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{1,k}, (d : B_k) \vdash^{w_{1,k}} Q_k :: (c : A_k)$ and $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} P :: (d : B_k)$.

By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_{1,k}, (d : B_k) \vDash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) :: (c : A_k) \quad \Delta_2 \vDash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (d : B_k)}{\Delta_{1,k}, \Delta_2 \vDash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q_k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P) :: (c : A_k)}$$

Case (C:&P):

$$\text{proc}(c, w_c, d..k ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) \xrightarrow{d, \& P} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k)$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B) \vdash^{w_1} d..k ; Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (d : B) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = w_1 + w_c + w_2 + w_d}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \vDash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, d..k ; Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (d : B)$ gives

$$\frac{\exists \{\Delta_{2,l}, w_{2,l}\}_{l \in L}, \quad (\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{2,l} \vdash^{w_{2,l}} P_l :: (d : B_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_2 = \sum_{l \in L}^L p_l \cdot \Delta_{2,l} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_2 = \sum_{l \in L} p_l \cdot w_{2,l}}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_2 \vdash^{w_2} \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L} :: (d : \& P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

such that $B = \& P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L}$.

Inversion on $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \& P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_1} d..k ; Q :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{(k \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : B_k) \vdash^{w_1} Q :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash p_k = 1 \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash p_j = 0 \quad (j \neq k)}{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_1, (d : \& P \{l^{P_l} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_1} d..k ; Q :: (c : A)}$$

From $\cdot ; \top \vDash p_k = 1$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash p_j = 0$ ($j \neq k$) we know that $\cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_2 = \Delta_{2,k}$ and $\cdot ; \top \vDash w_2 = w_{2,k}$.

For $k \in L$ there is $\cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{2,k} \vdash^{w_2,k} P_k :: (d : B_k)$, so by T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B_k) \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_{2,k} \Vdash^{w_2+w_d} \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k) :: (d : B_k)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_{2,k} \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_d, P_k) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:DIST):

$$\frac{(i_0 \in \mathcal{I}) \quad C_{i_0} \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} C'_{i_0}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}/\{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\})}$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_i}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

For $i_0 \in \mathcal{I}$ there are $\Delta_{i_0} \Vdash^{w_{i_0}} C_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0})$ and $C_{i_0} \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} C'_{i_0}$. By induction hyp. we have $\Delta_{i_0} \Vdash^{w_{i_0}} C'_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0})$.

Since the weights p_i remain the same after reduction, the following holds by T:DIST

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}/\{i_0\}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \Delta_{i_0} \Vdash^{w_{i_0}} C'_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0}) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}/\{i_0\}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i + p_{i_0} \cdot \Delta_{i_0} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}/\{i_0\}}^R p_i \cdot A_i + p_{i_0} \cdot A_{i_0} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}/\{i_0\}} p_i \cdot w_i + p_{i_0} \cdot w_{i_0}}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}/\{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\}) :: (c : A)}$$

Case (C:SDIST:R):

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} C'}{\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} C'}$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (d : B)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (d : B)$ gives

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_{2,i}} C_i :: (d : B_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_{2,i} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash B = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot B_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_{2,i}}{\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (d : B)}$$

Now by case analysis on the form of B . If B is not of the form $\oplus_P \{ \dots \}$, then from $\cdot ; \top \vDash B = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot B_i$ we know that $B = B_i$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$. So by T:COMPOSE, the following holds for any $i \in \mathcal{I}$

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_{2,i}} C_i :: (d : B)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_1+w_{2,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i :: (c : A)}$$

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_1, \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_1+w_{2,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_1, \Delta_{2,i}) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot (w_1 + w_{2,i})}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this sub-case.

If there is $B = \oplus_P \{ l^{p'_l} : B_l \}_{l \in L}$, then $B_i = \oplus_P \{ l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l \}_{l \in L}$ where $\cdot ; \top \vDash p'_l = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot p_{l,i}$. We now have $\Delta_1, (d : \oplus_P \{ l^{p'_l} : B_l \}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A)$.

Notice that C:DIST is the only rule that can derive the reduction $\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} C'$. So there exists some $i_0 \in \mathcal{I}$ such that $\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_{i_0} \xrightarrow{d,\kappa} C'_{i_0}$ and $\Delta_{2,i_0} \Vdash^{w_{2,i_0}} C_{i_0} :: (d : \oplus_P \{ l^{p_{l,i_0}} : B_l \}_{l \in L})$. From Lemma 7.9 we know that Q is of the form $\text{pcase } d \text{ } (\dots \Rightarrow \dots)$. Inversion on $\Delta_1, (d : \oplus_P \{ l^{p'_l} : B_l \}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{\exists \{ \Delta_{1,l}, A_l, w_{1,l} \}_{l \in L}, \quad (\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{1,l}, (d : B_l) \vdash^{w_{1,l}} Q_l :: (c : A_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_1 = \sum_{l \in L}^L p'_l \cdot \Delta_{1,l} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{l \in L}^R p'_l \cdot A_l \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 = w + \sum_{l \in L} p'_l \cdot w_{1,l}}{\Delta_1, (d : \oplus_P \{ l^{p'_l} : B_l \}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w, \text{pcase } d \text{ } (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) :: (c : A)}$$

For all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, define $\Delta'_{1,i} = \sum_{l \in L}^L p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{1,l}$, $A_i = \sum_{l \in L}^R p_{l,i} \cdot A_l$ and $w'_{1,i} = \sum_{l \in L} p_{l,i} \cdot w_{1,l}$.

By $\oplus_P L$ and T:PROC we have

$\exists \{\Delta_{1,l}, A_l, w_{1,l}\}_{l \in L}$,

$$\frac{(\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{1,l}, (d : B_l) \vdash^{w_{1,l}} Q_l :: (c : A_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta'_{1,i} = \sum_{l \in L}^L p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{1,l} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A_i = \sum_{l \in L}^R p_{l,i} \cdot A_l \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w'_{1,i} = \sum_{l \in L} p_{l,i} \cdot w_{1,l}}{\Delta'_{1,i}, (d : \oplus_P \{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w+w'_{1,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, \text{pcase } d (l \Rightarrow Q_l)_{l \in L}) :: (c : A_i)}$$

So $\Delta'_{1,i}, (d : B_i) \Vdash^{w+w'_{1,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A_i)$ holds. Additionally, we have the following equalities

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta'_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,i}) &= \sum_{i \in I}^L (p_i \cdot \sum_{l \in L}^L p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{1,l}), (p_i \cdot \Delta_{2,i}) \\ &= (\sum_{i \in I}^L \sum_{l \in L}^L p_i \cdot p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{1,l}), \Delta_2 \\ &= (\sum_{l \in L}^L \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{1,l}), \Delta_2 \\ &= (\sum_{l \in L}^L p'_l \cdot \Delta_{1,l}), \Delta_2 \\ &= \Delta_1, \Delta_2 \\ \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i &= \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot \sum_{l \in L}^R p_{l,i} \cdot A_l \\ &= \sum_{l \in L}^R \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot p_{l,i} \cdot A_l \\ &= \sum_{l \in L}^R p'_l \cdot A_l \\ &= A \\ \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot (w + w'_{1,i}) &= w + \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \sum_{l \in L} p_{l,i} \cdot w_{1,l} \\ &= w + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{l \in L} p_i \cdot p_{l,i} \cdot w_{1,l} \\ &= w + \sum_{i \in I} p'_i \cdot w_{1,l} \\ &= w_1 \end{aligned}$$

By T:COMPOSE we have

$$\frac{\Delta'_{1,i}, (d : B_i) \Vdash^{w+w'_{1,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) :: (c : A_i) \quad \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_{2,i}} C_i :: (d : B_i)}{\Delta'_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w+w'_{1,i}+w_{2,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i :: (c : A_i)}$$

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{(\forall i \in I) \quad \Delta'_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,i} \Vdash^{w+w'_{1,i}+w_{2,i}} \text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta'_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,i}) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot (w + w'_{1,i} + w_{2,i})}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{\text{proc}(c, w, Q) \parallel C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this case.

Case (C:SDIST:L):

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'}$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : B)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (c : A)}$$

Inversion on $\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)$ gives

$$\frac{(\forall i \in I) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_i) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, (d : B)) = \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_i)) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_{1,i}}{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)}$$

Now by case analysis on the form of B . If B is not of the form $\&P\{\dots\}$ then from $\cdot ; \top \vDash B = \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot B_i$ we know that $B = B_i$ for all $i \in I$. So by T:COMPOSE, the following holds for any $i \in I$

$$\frac{\Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_i) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : B)}{\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_2} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (c : A_i)}$$

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_2} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_2) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot (w_{1,i} + w_2)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this sub-case.

If there is $B = \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L}$, then $B_i = \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L}$ where $\cdot ; \top \vDash p'_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot p_{l,i}$. We now have $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})$.

Notice that C:DIST is the only rule that can derive the reduction $\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. So there exists some $i_0 \in \mathcal{I}$ such that $C_{i_0} \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'_i$ and $\Delta_{1,i_0}, (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i_0}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_{1,i_0}} C_{i_0} :: (c : A_{i_0})$. From Lemma 7.10 we know that P is of the form $\text{pcase } d \text{ } (\dots \Rightarrow \dots)$ or $d \leftrightarrow x$.

In the case of $P = d \leftrightarrow x$, we have $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, d \leftrightarrow x) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})$. By inversion, we have

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_2-w} d \leftrightarrow x :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w \leq w_2}{\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, d \leftrightarrow x) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

such that $\Delta_2 = (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})$.

For all $i \in \mathcal{I}$ there is $\cdot ; \top ; (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \vdash^{w_2-w} d \leftrightarrow x :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L})$. By T:PROC and T:COMPOSE we also have

$$\frac{\Delta_{1,i}, (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, d \leftrightarrow x) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L})}{\Delta_{1,i}, (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_2} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, d \leftrightarrow x) :: (c : A_i)}$$

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L}) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_2} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, d \leftrightarrow x) :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, (x : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L})) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot (w_{1,i} + w_2)}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, d \leftrightarrow x)) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this sub-case.

In the case that P is of the form $\text{pcase } d \text{ } (\dots \Rightarrow \dots)$, inversion on $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})$ gives

$$\frac{\exists \{\Delta_{2,l}, w_{2,l}\}_{l \in L} \quad (\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{2,l} \vdash^{w_{2,l}} P_l :: (d : B_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_2 = \sum_{l \in L}^L p'_l \cdot \Delta_{2,l} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w_2 = w + \sum_{l \in L} p'_l \cdot w_{2,l}}{\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, w, \text{pcase } d \text{ } (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p'_i} : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

For all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, define $\Delta'_{2,i} = \sum_{l \in L}^L p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{2,l}$ and $w'_{2,i} = \sum_{l \in L} p_{l,i} \cdot w_{2,l}$. By $\&_{\mathcal{P}}L$ and T:PROC we have

$$\frac{\exists \{\Delta_{2,l}, w_{2,l}\}_{l \in L} \quad (\forall l \in L) \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta_{2,l} \vdash^{w_{2,l}} P_l :: (d : B_l) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta'_{2,i} = \sum_{l \in L}^L p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{2,l} \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w'_{2,i} = \sum_{l \in L} p_{l,i} \cdot w_{2,l}}{\Delta'_{2,i} \Vdash^{w+w'_{2,i}} \text{proc}(d, w, \text{pcase } d \text{ } (l \Rightarrow P_l)_{l \in L}) :: (d : \&_{\mathcal{P}}\{l^{p_{l,i}} : B_l\}_{l \in L})}$$

So $\Delta'_{2,i} \Vdash^{w+w'_{2,i}} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : B_i)$ holds. Additionally, we have the following equalities

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta'_{2,i}) &= \Delta_1, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta'_{2,i} \\ &= \Delta_1, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \sum_{l \in L}^L p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{2,l} \\ &= \Delta_1, \sum_{l \in L}^L \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot p_{l,i} \cdot \Delta_{2,l} \\ &= \Delta_1, \sum_{l \in L}^L p'_l \cdot \Delta_{2,l} \\ &= \Delta_1, \Delta_2 \\ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot (w + w'_{2,i}) &= w + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot \sum_{l \in L} p_{l,i} \cdot w_{2,l} \\ &= w + \sum_{l \in L} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot p_{l,i} \cdot w_{2,l} \\ &= w + \sum_{l \in L} p'_l \cdot w_{2,l} \\ &= w_2 \end{aligned}$$

By T:COMPOSE the following holds for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$

$$\frac{\Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_i) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \Delta'_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_1+w_{2,i}} \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (d : B_i)}{\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta'_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_1+w_{2,i}} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (c : A_i)}$$

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, \Delta'_{2,i} \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_1+w_{2,i}} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash \Delta_1, \Delta_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta'_{2,i}) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot (w_{1,i} + w_1 + w_{2,i})}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this case.

Case (C:BDIST:D):

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel C'_j) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} C''}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} C''}$$

By inversion on the typing judgment, we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_{1,i}) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_i :: (c : A_i) \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash (\Delta_1, (d : B)) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_{1,i})) \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash w_1 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_{1,i} \end{array}}{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)} \quad \frac{\begin{array}{l} (\forall j \in \mathcal{J}) \quad \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_{2,j}} C'_j :: (d : B_{2,j}) \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash \Delta_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot \Delta_{2,j} \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash B = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^R p'_j \cdot B_{2,j} \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash w_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot w_{2,j} \end{array}}{\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (d : B)}$$

$$\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A)$$

From the reduction label d, det we know that $B \neq \oplus_p \{ \dots \}$ and $B \neq \&_p \{ \dots \}$, we have $B_{1,i} = B$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and $B_{2,j} = B$ for all $j \in \mathcal{J}$ by definition of weighted sums. For each $i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}$ we have $\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_{2,j}} C_i \parallel C'_j :: (c : A_i)$ by Lemma 7.6. Additionally we have the following equalities

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}^L (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,j}) &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}^L (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot \Delta_{1,i}, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}^L (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot \Delta_{2,j} \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_{1,i}, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot \Delta_{2,j} \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot \Delta_1, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_2 \\ &= \Delta_1, \Delta_2 \\ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}^R (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot A_i &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^R p'_j \cdot \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^R p'_j \cdot A \\ &= A \\ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (w_{1,i} + w_{2,j}) &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot w_{1,i} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot w_{2,j} \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_{1,i} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot w_{2,j} \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot w_1 + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_2 \\ &= w_1 + w_2 \end{aligned}$$

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\forall i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_{2,j}} C_i \parallel C'_j :: (c : A_i) \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash (\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}^L (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_{2,j}) \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}^R (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot A_i \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (w_{1,i} + w_{2,j}) \end{array}}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel C'_j) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C'' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this case.

Case (C:BDIST:R):

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel C'_j) : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \&P} C''}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \&P} C''}$$

By inversion on the typing judgement, we have

$$\frac{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A) \quad \begin{array}{l} (\forall j \in \mathcal{J}) \quad \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_{2,j}} C'_j :: (d : B_{2,j}) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot \Delta_{2,j} \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash B = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^R p'_j \cdot B_{2,j} \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot w_{2,j} \end{array}}{\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (d : B)} \quad \frac{}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A)}$$

From the reduction label $d, \&P$ we know that $B = \&P\{P^i : B_i\}_{i \in L}$, we have $B_{2,j} = B$ for all $j \in \mathcal{J}$ by the definition of weighted sum. For each $j \in \mathcal{J}$ we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_1+w_{2,j}} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel C'_j :: (c : A)$ by T:COMPOSE.

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\forall j \in \mathcal{J}) \quad \Delta_1, \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_1+w_{2,j}} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel C'_j :: (c : A) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot (\Delta_1, \Delta_{2,j}) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^R p'_j \cdot A \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot (w_1 + w_{2,j}) \end{array}}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel C'_j) : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C'' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this case.

Case (C:BDIST:L):

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}})) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus P} C''}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus P} C''}$$

By inversion on the typing judgement we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_{1,i}) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_i :: (c : A_i) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, (d : B)) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_{1,i})) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_{1,i} \end{array}}{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)} \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (d : B) \quad \frac{}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A)}$$

From the reduction label $d, \oplus P$ we know that $B = \oplus P\{P^i : B_i\}_{i \in L}$, we have $B_{1,i} = B$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$ by the definition of weighted sum. For each $i \in \mathcal{I}$ we have $\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_2} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A_i)$ by T:COMPOSE.

By T:DIST we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_{1,i}+w_2} C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (c : A_i) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash (\Delta_1, \Delta_2) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, \Delta_2) \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash w_1 + w_2 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot (w_{1,i} + w_2) \end{array}}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}})) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

By the induction hyp. we have $\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} C'' :: (c : A)$ which concludes this case. \square

8 PROGRESS

LEMMA 8.1. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then $FV^L(C) = \text{dom}(\Delta)$ and $FV^R(C) = \text{dom}(\Gamma)$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$.

Case (T:PROC):

$$\frac{\cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w-w_c} P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash 0 \leq w_c}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, w_c, P) :: (c : A)}$$

where $C = \text{proc}(c, w_c, P)$ and $\Gamma = (c : A)$.

We now have $FV^L(\text{proc}(c, w_c, P)) = FV(P) \setminus \{c\} = \text{dom}(\Delta)$ and $FV^R(\text{proc}(c, w_c, P)) = \{c\} = \text{dom}(\Gamma)$.

Case (T:DIST):

$$\frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \Delta = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash w = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_i}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

where $C = \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$ and $\Gamma = (c : A)$.

By induction hyp. we have the following equalities

$$\begin{aligned} FV^L(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}})) &= \bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} FV^L(C_i) = \bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \text{dom}(\Delta_i) \\ FV^R(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}})) &= \bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} FV^R(C_i) = \bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{c\} = \{c\} \end{aligned}$$

From $\cdot \top \vDash \Delta = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L \Delta_i$ we know that $\text{dom}(\Delta) = \text{dom}(\Delta_i)$ so $\bigcup_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \text{dom}(\Delta_i) = \text{dom}(\Delta)$.

Case (T:COMPOSE):

$$\frac{\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C :: (\Delta, \Delta')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C) :: (\Delta, (c : A))}$$

We have the following equalities by definition of FV

$$\begin{aligned} FV^L(O \parallel C) &= (FV^L(O) \cup FV^L(C)) \setminus FV^R(C) \\ FV^R(O \parallel C) &= (FV^R(O) \cup FV^R(C)) \setminus FV^L(O) \end{aligned}$$

By induction hyp. we have

$$\begin{aligned} FV^L(O) &= \text{dom}(\Delta_1, \Delta') & FV^R(O) &= \{c\} \\ FV^L(C) &= \text{dom}(\Delta_2) & FV^R(C) &= \text{dom}(\Delta, \Delta') \end{aligned}$$

which shows

$$\begin{aligned} (FV^L(O) \cup FV^L(C)) \setminus FV^R(C) &= (\text{dom}(\Delta_1, \Delta') \cup \text{dom}(\Delta_2)) \setminus \text{dom}(\Delta, \Delta') = \text{dom}(\Delta_1, \Delta_2) \\ (FV^R(O) \cup FV^R(C)) \setminus FV^L(O) &= (\{c\} \cup \text{dom}(\Delta, \Delta')) \setminus \text{dom}(\Delta_1, \Delta') = \text{dom}(\Delta, (c : A)) \end{aligned}$$

□

LEMMA 8.2. *If C live, then there exists C' such that $C \mapsto C'$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of C live. For cases L:FLIP and L:DEF the conclusion is immediate.

Case (L:DIST):

$$\frac{(i_0 \in \mathcal{I}) \quad C_{i_0} \text{ live}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \text{ live}}$$

By induction hyp. there is $C_{i_0} \mapsto C'_{i_0}$. By E:DIST we have $C \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\})$.

Case (L:COMPOSE:H):

$$\frac{O \text{ live}}{(O \parallel C') \text{ live}}$$

By induction hyp. there is $O \mapsto O'$. By multiset rewriting we have $C \mapsto O' \parallel C'$.

Case (L:COMPOSE:T):

$$\frac{C' \text{ live}}{(O \parallel C') \text{ live}}$$

By induction hyp. there is $C' \mapsto C''$. By multiset rewriting we have $C \mapsto O \parallel C''$. \square

LEMMA 8.3. *If C (d, κ)-poised and $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then $d \in \text{dom}(\Gamma)$ and $\kappa \succ \text{sort}(\Gamma(d))$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of C (d, κ)-poised, followed by inversion on $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$. The majority of cases are immediate with the exceptions of PR:DIST, PR:COMPOSE:H and PR:COMPOSE:T.

Case (PR:DIST):

$$\frac{(i_0 \in \mathcal{I}) \quad C_{i_0} \text{ (d, κ)-poised}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \text{ (d, κ)-poised}} \quad \frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash \Delta = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash w = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_i}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)}$$

where $C = \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$ and $\Gamma = (c : A)$.

By induction hyp. with C_{i_0} we have $d = c$ and $\kappa \succ \text{sort}(A_{i_0}) = \text{sort}(A)$.

Case (PR:COMPOSE:H):

$$\frac{O \text{ (d, κ)-poised}}{(O \parallel C') \text{ (d, κ)-poised}} \quad \frac{\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C' :: (\Gamma', \Delta')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C') :: (\Gamma', (c : A))}$$

where $C = (O \parallel C')$, $\Delta = (\Delta_1, \Delta_2)$ and $\Gamma = (\Gamma', (c : A))$.

By induction hyp. with O we have $d = c$ and $\kappa \succ \text{sort}(A)$.

Case (PR:COMPOSE:T):

$$\frac{C' \text{ (d, κ)-poised} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^L(O)}{(O \parallel C') \text{ (d, κ)-poised}} \quad \frac{\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C' :: (\Gamma', \Delta')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C') :: (\Gamma', (c : A))}$$

where $C = (O \parallel C')$, $\Delta = (\Delta_1, \Delta_2)$ and $\Gamma = (\Gamma', (c : A))$.

By induction hyp. with C' we have $d \in \text{dom}(\Gamma', \Delta')$ and $\kappa \succ \text{sort}((\Gamma', \Delta')(d))$. From $d \notin \text{FV}^L(O)$ and Lemma 8.1 we know that $d \notin \text{dom}(\Delta')$. So there must be $d \in \text{dom}(\Gamma')$ and $\kappa \succ \text{sort}(\Gamma'(d))$. \square

LEMMA 8.4. *If C (d, κ)-blocked and $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta)$ and $\kappa = \text{sort}(\Delta(d))$.*

PROOF. Similar to the proof of Lemma 8.3. \square

LEMMA 8.5. *If $C = (C_1 \parallel C_2)$ such that C_1 (d, κ)-blocked, C_2 (d, κ)-poised (or C_2 (d, \top)-poised), $\Delta_1, \Delta', (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} C_1 :: \Gamma_1$, $\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C_2 :: (\Gamma_2, \Delta', (d : B))$, and $\kappa = \text{sort}(B)$, then there exists C' such that $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$ holds.*

PROOF. By nested induction on C_1 (d, κ)-blocked and C_2 (d, κ)-poised, followed by inversion on the typing judgments.

Case:

$$\frac{\frac{C_{1,i_0} \text{ (d, κ)-blocked}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_{1,i} : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \text{ (d, κ)-blocked}} \text{BL:DIST} \quad \frac{(\forall i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_i) \Vdash^{w_{1,i}} C_{1,i} :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash (\Delta_1, (d : B)) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \cdot (\Delta_{1,i}, (d : B_i)) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash w_1 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i \cdot w_{1,i}}{\Delta_1, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, \{C_{1,i} : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) :: (c : A)} \text{T:DIST}}{\frac{C'_{2,j_0} \text{ (d, κ)-poised}}{\text{proc}(d, \{C'_{2,j} : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \text{ (d, κ)-poised}} \text{PR:DIST}} \quad \frac{(\forall j \in \mathcal{J}) \quad \Delta_{2,j} \Vdash^{w_{2,j}} C'_{2,j} :: (d : B'_j) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash \Delta_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^L p'_j \cdot \Delta_{2,j} \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash B = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}}^R p'_j \cdot B'_j \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash w_2 = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot w_{2,j}}{\Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} \text{proc}(d, \{C'_{2,j} : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) :: (d : B)} \text{T:DIST}}$$

where $C_1 = \text{proc}(c, \{C_{1,i} : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$, $C_2 = \text{proc}(d, \{C'_{2,j} : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}})$, $\Delta' = \cdot$, $\Gamma_1 = (c : A)$ and $\Gamma_2 = \cdot$.

By case analysis on κ .

- If $\kappa = \text{det}$, then we know that $B \neq \oplus_P\{\dots\}$ and $B \neq \&_P\{\dots\}$. So we have $B_i = B$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and $B'_j = B$ for $j \in \mathcal{J}$. By induction hyp. with C_{1,i_0}, C'_{2,j_0} we have $(C_{1,i_0} \parallel C'_{2,j_0}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} . Application of C:DIST and C:DIST:D yields $C \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_{1,i} \parallel C'_{2,j}) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}, i \neq i_0 \vee j \neq j_0} \# \{\mathcal{D} : p_{i_0} \cdot p'_{j_0}\})$.
- If $\kappa = \oplus_P$, then we know that $B = \oplus_P\{\dots\}$. So we have $B_i = B$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$. By induction hyp. with C_{1,i_0}, C_2 we have $(C_{1,i_0} \parallel C_2) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus_P} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} . Application of C:DIST and C:BDIST:L yields $C \xrightarrow{d, \oplus_P} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_{1,i} \parallel C_2) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{\mathcal{D} : p_{i_0}\})$.
- If $\kappa = \&_P$ then we know that $B = \&_P\{\dots\}$. So we have $B'_j = B$ for all $j \in \mathcal{J}$. By induction hyp. with C_1, C'_{2,j_0} we have $(C_1, C'_{2,j_0}) \xrightarrow{d, \&_P} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} . Application of C:DIST and C:BDIST:R yields $C \xrightarrow{d, \&_P} \text{proc}(c, \{(C_1 \parallel C'_{2,j}) : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J} \setminus \{j_0\}} \# \{\mathcal{D} : p'_{j_0}\})$.

Case:

$$\frac{\frac{O_1 (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^R(C'_1)}{(O_1 \parallel C'_1) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:COMPOSE:H} \quad \frac{\Delta_{11}, \Delta'_1, \Omega, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} O_1 :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_{12}, \Delta'_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C'_1 :: (\Gamma'_1, \Omega)}{\Delta_{11}, \Delta_{12}, \Delta'_1, \Delta'_2, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O_1, \parallel C'_1) :: (\Gamma'_1, (c : A))} \text{T:COMPOSE}}{} \text{BL:COMPOSE:H}$$

where $C_1 = (O_1, \parallel C'_1)$, $\Delta_1 = (\Delta_{11}, \Delta_{12})$, $\Delta' = (\Delta'_1, \Delta'_2)$ and $\Gamma_1 = (\Gamma'_1, (c : A))$.

By Lemma 8.4 with O_1 , Lemma 8.1 and $d \notin \text{FV}^R(C'_1)$, d can only be placed in the way shown above.

By induction hyp. with O_1, C_2 we have $(O_1 \parallel C_2) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} .

Then $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}$ by multiset rewriting.

Case:

$$\frac{\frac{C'_1 (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}}{(O_1 \parallel C'_1) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:COMPOSE:T} \quad \frac{\Delta_{11}, \Delta'_1, \Omega \Vdash^{w_1} O_1 :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_{12}, \Delta'_2, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_2} C'_1 :: (\Gamma'_1, \Omega)}{\Delta_{11}, \Delta_{12}, \Delta'_1, \Delta'_2, (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O_1 \parallel C'_1) :: (\Gamma'_1, (c : A))} \text{T:COMPOSE}}{} \text{BL:COMPOSE:T}$$

where $C_1 = (O_1 \parallel C'_1)$, $\Delta_1 = (\Delta_{11}, \Delta_{12})$, $\Delta' = (\Delta'_1, \Delta'_2)$ and $\Gamma_1 = (\Gamma'_1, (c : A))$.

By Lemma 8.4 with C'_1 , d can only be placed in the way shown above.

By induction hyp. with C'_1, C_2 we have $(C'_1 \parallel C_2) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} .

Then $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} O_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}$ by multiset rewriting.

Case:

$$\frac{\frac{\dots}{\text{proc}(c, w_c, Q(d)) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\dots \quad \frac{\dots}{\Delta_1, \Delta', (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q(d)) :: (c : A)} \text{T:}\dots}{\frac{O_2 (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}}{(O_2 \parallel C'_2) (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:COMPOSE:H} \quad \frac{\Delta_{21}, \Omega \Vdash^{w_{21}} O_2 :: (d : B) \quad \Delta_{22} \Vdash^{w_{22}} C'_2 :: (\Gamma_2, \Delta', \Omega)}{\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{22} \Vdash^{w_{21}+w_{22}} (O_2 \parallel C'_2) :: (\Gamma_2, \Delta', (d : B))} \text{T:COMPOSE}}{} \text{PR:COMPOSE:H}$$

where $C_1 = \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q(d))$, $C_2 = (O_2 \parallel C'_2)$, $\Gamma_1 = (c : A)$ and $\Delta_2 = (\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{22})$.

By Lemma 8.3 with O_2 , d can only be placed in the way shown above.

By induction hyp. with C_1, O_2 we have $(C_1 \parallel O_2) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} .

Then $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D} \parallel C'_2$ by multiset rewriting.

Case: C_1 is a leaf and C_2 is a sequence of objects.

•

$$\frac{\frac{\dots}{\text{proc}(c, w_c, Q(d)) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}} \text{BL:}\dots \quad \frac{\dots}{\Delta'', (d : B), (x : C) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q(d)) :: (c : A)} \text{T:}\dots}{\frac{C'_2 (d, \kappa)\text{-poised} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^L(O_2)}{(O_2 \parallel C'_2) (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}} \text{PR:COMPOSE:T} \quad \frac{\Delta_{21}, \Omega \Vdash^{w_{21}} O_2 :: (x : C) \quad \Delta_{22} \Vdash^{w_{22}} C'_2 :: (\Gamma_2, \Delta'', (d : B), \Omega)}{\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{22} \Vdash^{w_{21}+w_{22}} (O_2 \parallel C'_2) :: (\Gamma_2, \Delta'', (d : B), (x : C))} \text{T:COMPOSE}}{} \text{PR:COMPOSE:T}$$

where $C_1 = \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q(d))$, $C_2 = (O_2 \parallel C'_2)$, $\Delta' = (\Delta'', (x : C))$, $\Gamma_1 = (c : A)$ and $\Delta_2 = (\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{22})$.

By Lemma 8.3 with C'_2 , Lemma 8.1 and $d \notin \text{FV}^L(O_2)$, d can only be placed in the way shown above.

By induction hyp. with C_1, C'_2 we have $(C_1, C'_2) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} .

Then $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D} \parallel O_2$ by multiset rewriting.

•

$$\frac{\dots}{\text{proc}(c, w_c, Q\langle d \rangle) \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-blocked}} \text{BL:}\dots \quad \frac{\dots}{\Delta', (d : B) \Vdash^{w_1} \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q\langle d \rangle) :: (c : A)} \text{T:}\dots \quad \frac{C'_2 \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-poised} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^L(O_2)}{(O_2 \parallel C'_2) \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-poised}} \text{PR:COMPOSE:T}$$

$$\frac{\Delta_{21}, \Omega \Vdash^{w_{21}} O_2 :: (x : C) \quad \Delta_{22} \Vdash^{w_{22}} C'_2 :: (\Gamma'_2, \Delta', (d : B), \Omega)}{\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{22} \Vdash^{w_{21}+w_{22}} (O_2 \parallel C'_2) :: (\Gamma'_2, \Delta', (d : B), (x : C))} \text{T:COMPOSE}$$

where $C_1 = \text{proc}(c, w_c, Q\langle d \rangle)$, $C_2 = (O_2 \parallel C'_2)$, $\Gamma_1 = (c : A)$, $\Delta_2 = (\Delta_{21}, \Delta_{22})$ and $\Gamma_2 = (\Gamma'_2, (x : C))$.

By induction hyp. with C_1, C'_2 we have $(C_1 \parallel C'_2) \xRightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D}$ for some \mathcal{D} .

Then $C \xRightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{D} \parallel O_2$ by multiset rewriting. □

LEMMA 8.6. *If $\cdot \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$ and C (d, κ) -comm, then there exists C' such that $C \xRightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$ holds.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of C (d, κ) -comm followed by inversion on $\cdot \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$.

Case:

$$\frac{C_{i_0} \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-comm}}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-comm}} \text{CM:DIST} \quad \frac{(\forall i \in I) \cdot \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \Vdash w = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i}{\cdot \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)} \text{T:DIST}$$

By induction hyp. we have $C_{i_0} \xRightarrow{d, \kappa} C'_{i_0}$ for some C'_{i_0} .

By C:DIST we have $C \xRightarrow{d, \kappa} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\})$.

Case:

$$\frac{O \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-blocked} \quad C_2 \text{ (} d, \kappa' \text{)-poised} \quad \kappa <: \kappa'}{(O \parallel C_2) \text{ (} d, \kappa \text{)-comm}} \text{CM:COMPOSE:C} \quad \frac{\Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \cdot \Vdash^{w_2} C_2 :: (\Gamma, \Delta')}{\cdot \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C_2) :: (\Gamma, (c : A))} \text{T:COMPOSE}$$

By Lemma 8.4 with O , we know that $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta')$ and $\kappa = \text{sort}(\Delta'(d))$. Lemma 8.5 concludes the proof. □

LEMMA 8.7. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$ and C poised, then for all $d \in \text{dom}(\Gamma)$, it holds that C $(d, \text{sort}(\Gamma(d)))$ -poised (or C (d, \top) -poised).*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$ followed by inversion on C poised. □

LEMMA 8.8. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then at least one of the cases below holds.*

- (1) C live
- (2) C (d, κ) -comm for some d, κ
- (3) C $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta(d)))$ -blocked for some $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta)$
- (4) C poised

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$.

Case (T:PROC):

$$\frac{\cdot ; \Vdash \Delta \vdash^{w'} P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \Vdash 0 \leq w}{\Delta \Vdash^{w+w'} \text{proc}(c, w, P) :: (c : A)}$$

By case analysis on P we can conclude that either $\text{proc}(c, w, P)$ live, $\text{proc}(c, w, P)$ $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta(d)))$ -blocked for some $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta)$ or $\text{proc}(c, w, P)$ poised.

Case (T:DIST):

$$\frac{(\forall i \in I) \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \quad \cdot ; \Vdash \Delta = \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i \quad \cdot ; \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i \quad \cdot ; \Vdash w = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)}$$

Apply induction hyp. on all C_i 's. If all C_i 's are poised, then C is poised by P:DIST.

Otherwise there exists i_0 such that C_{i_0} is not poised. The following situations are possible.

- If C_{i_0} live, then C live by L:DIST.
- If C_{i_0} (d, κ) -comm for some d, κ , then C (d, κ) -comm by CM:DIST.
- If C_{i_0} $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta_{i_0}(d)))$ -blocked for some $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta_{i_0})$, then C $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta(d)))$ -blocked by BL:DIST.

Case (T:COMPOSE):

$$\frac{\Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C_2 :: (\Gamma, \Delta')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C_2) :: (\Gamma, (c : A))}$$

Apply induction hyp. on O and C_2 .

- If O live or C_2 live, then C live by L:COMPOSE:H or L:COMPOSE:T.
- If O (d, κ) -comm or C_2 (d, κ) -comm for some d, κ , then C (d, κ) -comm by CM:COMPOSE:H or CM:COMPOSE:T.
- If C_2 $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta_2(d)))$ -blocked for some $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta_2)$, then C $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta_2(d)))$ -blocked by BL:COMPOSE:T.
- If O $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta_1(d)))$ -blocked for some $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta_1)$, then C $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta_1(d)))$ -blocked by BL:COMPOSE:H and $d \notin \text{FV}^R(C_2)$ (because $d \notin \text{dom}(\Gamma, \Delta')$ and Lemma 8.1).
- If O $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta'(d)))$ -blocked for some $d \in \text{dom}(\Delta')$ and C_2 poised, then by Lemma 8.7 we have C_2 $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta'(d)))$ -poised. By CM:COMPOSE:C we have C $(d, \text{sort}(\Delta'(d)))$ -comm.
- If both O and C_2 are poised, then by P:COMPOSE C is poised.

LEMMA 8.9. *If $\cdot \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then at least one the following cases holds* □

- (1) C live
- (2) C (d, κ) -comm for some d, κ
- (3) C poised

PROOF. By Lemma 8.8. □

THEOREM 8.10 (GLOBAL PROGRESS). *If $\cdot \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then either*

- (1) $C \mapsto C'$ for some C' , or $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$ for some C', d, κ
- (2) C poised

PROOF. By Lemmas 8.2, 8.6 and 8.9. □

9 FLATTENING AND SIMULATION

Flatten nested configurations.

$$\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, P) \approx \{\text{proc}(c, w, P) : 1\}} \text{FL:PROC} \qquad \frac{\forall i \in I : C_i \approx \mu_i}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \approx \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i} \text{FL:DIST}$$

$$\frac{O \approx \mu_1 \quad C \approx \mu_2}{(O \parallel C) \approx \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : \mu_1(\mathcal{D}_1) \cdot \mu_2(\mathcal{D}_2)\}_{\mathcal{D}_1 \in \text{dom}(\mu_1), \mathcal{D}_2 \in \text{dom}(\mu_2)}} \text{FL:COMPOSE}$$

THEOREM 9.1 (SIMULATION). *If $C \approx \mu$, $C' \approx \mu'$ and $C \mapsto C'$ or $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$, then $\mu \Rightarrow \mu'$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $C \mapsto C'$ or $C \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} C'$. Most cases are trivial as they have corresponding \mapsto det or \mapsto prob rules which can be lifted to \Rightarrow . We will only consider the interesting cases. These proofs will sometimes use the Haskell style \gg notation when composing operations on distributions.

Case:

$$\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{\text{proc}(c, w, P_H) : p, \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) : 1 - p\})} \text{(E:FLIP)}$$

We have $\mu = \{\text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) : 1\}$ and $\mu' = \{\text{proc}(c, w, P_H) : p, \text{proc}(c, w, P_T) : (1 - p)\}$

By SP:Flip we have $\text{proc}(c, w, \text{flip } p (H \Rightarrow P_H \mid T \Rightarrow P_T)) \xrightarrow{\text{prob}} \mu'$ which is immediately lifted to $\mu \Rightarrow \mu'$.

Case:

$$\frac{}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \mapsto \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\})} \text{(E:DIST)}$$

By inversion on $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \approx \mu$ we have $\mu = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i$ where $C_i \approx \mu_i$.

By inversion $\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{C'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\}) \approx \mu'$ we have $\mu' = \sum_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} p_i \cdot \mu_i + p_{i_0} \cdot \mu'_{i_0}$ where $C'_{i_0} \approx \mu'_{i_0}$.

By induction hyp. we have $\mu_{i_0} \Rightarrow \mu'_{i_0}$. Inversion on $\mu_{i_0} \Rightarrow \mu'_{i_0}$ and $C_{i_0} \mapsto C'_{i_0}$ implies that there exists \mathcal{D} in the domain of μ_{i_0} which can take a prob step. So we have $\sum_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} p_i \cdot \mu_i + p_{i_0} \cdot \mu_{i_0} \Rightarrow \sum_{i \in I \setminus \{i_0\}} p_i \cdot \mu_i + p_{i_0} \cdot \mu'_{i_0}$.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel C_j) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in I, j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} C''}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} C''} \text{(C:BDIST:D)}$$

Let $C_i \approx \mu_i$ for each $i \in I$ and $C'_j \approx \mu'_j$ for each $j \in \mathcal{J}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) &\approx (\sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i) \otimes (\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \\ &= \sum_{i \in I, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (\mu_i \otimes \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \\ \text{proc}(c, \{(C_i \parallel C'_j) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in I, j \in \mathcal{J}}) &\approx \sum_{i \in I, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (\mu_i \otimes \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \end{aligned}$$

From the induction hyp. we can immediately conclude $\mu \Rightarrow \mu'$.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel C'_j) : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \&p} C''}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \&p} C''} \text{(C:BDIST:R)}$$

Let $C_i \approx \mu_i$ for each $i \in I$ and $C'_j \approx \mu'_j$ for each $j \in \mathcal{J}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) &\approx (\sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i) \otimes (\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \\ &= \sum_{i \in I, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (\mu_i \otimes \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \\ \text{proc}(c, \{(\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \parallel C'_j) : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) &\approx \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot ((\sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i) \otimes \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} p'_j \cdot (\sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot (\mu_i \otimes \mu'_j)) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \\ &= \sum_{i \in I, j \in \mathcal{J}} (p_i \cdot p'_j) \cdot (\mu_i \otimes \mu'_j) \gg \lambda(\mathcal{D}_1, \mathcal{D}_2). \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : 1\} \end{aligned}$$

From the induction hyp. we can immediately conclude $\mu \Rightarrow \mu'$. □

10 EXPECTED COST ANALYSIS

Reasoning for expected cost analysis is carried out using the distribution-based semantics (Section 6). We begin by presenting the formal definition of the total work performed by some configuration \mathcal{D} , and the notion of *expected total work* [4].

Definition 10.1 (Total Work). Given a non-nested configuration $\mathcal{D} = \overline{\text{proc}(c_i, w_i, P_i)}$, we define the total work it has done as $\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) := \sum_i w_i$.

Definition 10.2 (Expected Total Work). For some well-typed configuration \mathcal{D}_0 , its *expected* total work is defined as $\text{etw}(\mathcal{D}_0) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\text{work}(\mathcal{D}_n)]$ where $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Markov chain constructed from \mathcal{D}_0 as the initial state and $\xrightarrow{\text{prob}}$ as the kernel.

LEMMA 10.3. *If $C \approx \mu$, $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$, then $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D} \sim \mu}[\text{work}(\mathcal{D})] \leq w$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $C \approx \mu$ followed by inversion on $\Delta \Vdash^w C :: \Gamma$.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{(FL:PROC)}}{\text{proc}(c, w_c, P) \approx \delta(\text{proc}(c, w_c, P))} \quad \frac{\text{(T:PROC)} \quad \cdot ; \top ; \Delta \vdash^{w_1} P :: (c : A) \quad \cdot ; \top \Vdash 0 \leq w_c}{\Delta \Vdash^{w_1+w_c} \text{proc}(c, w_c, P) :: (c : A)}$$

From Lemma 10.3 we know that $w_1 \geq 0$ which means that $w_1 + w_c \geq w_c = \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \delta(\text{proc}(c, w_c, P))]\text{work}(\mathcal{D})$.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{(FL:DIST)} \quad \forall i \in I : C_i \approx \mu_i}{\text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) \approx \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i} \quad \frac{\text{(T:DIST)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall i \in I : \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} C_i :: (c : A_i) \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash \Delta = \sum_{i \in I}^L p_i \cdot \Delta_i \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash A = \sum_{i \in I}^R p_i \cdot A_i \\ \cdot ; \top \Vdash w = \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i \end{array}}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{proc}(c, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in I}) :: (c : A)}$$

By induction hyp. for each $i \in I$ we have $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \mu_i]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) \leq w_i$. The following (in)equalities hold.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mu_i]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) &= \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \mu_i]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) \\ &\leq \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot w_i \\ &= w \end{aligned}$$

Case:

$$\frac{\text{(FL:COMPOSE)} \quad O \approx \mu_1 \quad C \approx \mu_2}{(O \parallel C) \approx \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : \mu_1(\mathcal{D}_1) \cdot \mu_2(\mathcal{D}_2)\}_{\mathcal{D}_1 \in \text{dom}(\mu_1), \mathcal{D}_2 \in \text{dom}(\mu_2)}} \quad \frac{\text{(T:COMPOSE)} \quad \Delta_1, \Delta' \Vdash^{w_1} O :: (c : A) \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C :: (\Gamma, \Delta')}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O \parallel C) :: (\Gamma, (c : A))}$$

By induction we have $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \mu_1]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) \leq w_1$ and $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \mu_2]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) \leq w_2$.

Let $\mu = \{(\mathcal{D}_1 \parallel \mathcal{D}_2) : \mu_1(\mathcal{D}_1) \cdot \mu_2(\mathcal{D}_2)\}_{\mathcal{D}_1 \in \text{dom}(\mu_1), \mathcal{D}_2 \in \text{dom}(\mu_2)}$. The following (in)equalities hold.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D} \sim \mu]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}) &= \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_1 \sim \mu_1, \mathcal{D}_2 \sim \mu_2]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}_1) + \text{work}(\mathcal{D}_2) \\ &= \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_1 \sim \mu_1]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}_1) + \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_2 \sim \mu_2]\text{work}(\mathcal{D}_2) \\ &\leq w_1 + w_2 \\ &= w \end{aligned}$$

□

THEOREM 10.4 (EXPECTED COST BOUND). *Given some well-typed configuration $\cdot \Vdash^w \mathcal{D}_0 :: \Gamma$, there is upper bound $\text{etw}(\mathcal{D}_0) \leq w$ on the expected total work performed by \mathcal{D}_0 .*

PROOF. Since the configurations here are refinement closed, the procedure of bounding resource usage in PreST follows the same reasoning as described in the technical report of NomosPro [3].

We begin by constructing the Markov chain $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. Starting from \mathcal{D}_0 which is well-typed in an empty context, applying Theorems 7.11, 7.12 and 8.10 gives us a sequence of hidden states $\{C_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ by iterating the reduction relations \mapsto and $\xrightarrow{d, \kappa}$. Due to the preservation theorems (Theorems 7.11 and 7.12), there is $\cdot \Vdash^w C_n :: \Gamma$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Applying Theorem 9.1 gives us a sequence of distributions $\{\mu_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ where $C_n \approx \mu_n$ and $\mu_n \Rightarrow \mu_{n+1}$. From the definition of \Rightarrow we know that there exists some $\mathcal{D}_n \in \text{dom}(\mu_n)$. So the sequence $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Markov chain with \mathcal{D}_0 as the initial state and $\xrightarrow{\text{prob}}$ as the kernel. From Lemma 10.3 we know that $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D} \sim \mu_n}[\text{work}(\mathcal{D})] \leq w$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $Q_n := \text{work}(\mathcal{D}_n)$ for each

$n \in \mathbb{N}$. Because work is nonnegative, $\{Q_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ forms a nonnegative, monotone, real-valued stochastic process such that $\mathbb{E}[Q_n] \leq w$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, with respect to the Markov chain $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$.

Termination time T is a random variable defined on the Markov chain $\{\mathcal{D}_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ as $T(\omega) := \inf\{\omega_n \text{ poised} \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Define random variable $Q_T(\omega) := Q_{T(\omega)}$ which represents the total work performed by trace ω until termination. Thus, the expected total work of all traces is $\mathbb{E}[Q_T]$. Define $Q_n^T(\omega) := Q_{\min(T(\omega, n))}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then we have $Q_T = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_n^T$ and $Q_n^T \leq Q_n$ by the monotonicity of $\{Q_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. By *Monotone Convergence Theorem* [5], we have $\mathbb{E}[Q_T] = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[Q_n^T] \leq w$. \square

11 CONSISTENCY

11.1 Monitor Process

To prove that probabilistic channels indeed produce distributions of messages described by their channels, we utilize a *monitor process* to record messages and show that the distribution of recorded messages is correct. A monitor process has the following syntax:

$$M ::= \text{record } x \mid \text{wait } x \text{ with } k \mid \text{stop } k$$

After composing a monitor with a configuration C that providing a probabilistic channel x . The record x construct receives a label $k \in L$ over channel $x : \oplus_P\{\ell^{P_\ell} : \mathbf{1}\}_{\ell \in L}$ and transitions to wait x with k where communication with C is synchronized for closing. Once channel x is closed, wait x with k transitions to stop k .

Monitor are typed using the judgment $(x : B) \vdash M \rightsquigarrow A$. The type A here describes the original type of channel x when M began monitoring. The type B describes the current type of x after monitoring has started. The rules for typing monitor processes are as follows:

RECORD	WAIT	STOP
$(x : \oplus_P\{\ell^{P_\ell} : \mathbf{1}\}_{\ell \in L}) \vdash \text{record } x \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P\{\ell^{P_\ell} : \mathbf{1}\}_{\ell \in L}$	$(x : \mathbf{1}) \vdash \text{wait } x \text{ with } k \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P\{\ell^{P_\ell} : \mathbf{1}\}_{\ell \in L}$	$\cdot \vdash \text{stop } k \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P\{\ell^{P_\ell} : \mathbf{1}\}_{\ell \in L}$

11.2 Monitor Configuration

A monitor configuration \mathcal{M} is nested multiverse configuration C composed with a monitor semantic object \mathcal{O}_M . Formally, monitor configurations are defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{E}_M ::= (w, M) \mid \{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \quad \mathcal{O}_M ::= \text{monitor}(\mathcal{E}_M) \quad \mathcal{M} ::= \mathcal{O}_M \parallel C$$

Monitor configurations use typing judgment $\Delta \Vdash^w \mathcal{M} \rightsquigarrow A$. Similarly to monitor process typing, type A here is the original type of the monitored channel.

TM:PROC	TM:DIST	
$\Delta \vdash M \rightsquigarrow A$	$\forall (i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} \mathcal{M}_i \rightsquigarrow A_i$	$\forall (i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} \mathcal{M}_i \rightsquigarrow A_i$
$\Delta \Vdash^w \text{monitor}(w, M) \rightsquigarrow A$	$\cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^L p_i \Delta_i = \Delta \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}}^R p_i A_i = A \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} p_i * w_i = w$	$\Delta \Vdash \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \rightsquigarrow A$
	TM:COMPOSE	
	$\Delta_1, \Delta \Vdash^{w_1} \mathcal{O}_M \rightsquigarrow A \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C :: \Delta$	
	$\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) \rightsquigarrow A$	

Status judgments (Section 4) are extended to account for monitor configurations.

PM:STOP	PM:DIST	PM:COMPOSE	LM:DIST
$\text{monitor}(w, \text{stop } k) \text{ poised}$	$\forall (i \in \mathcal{I}) \quad \mathcal{M}_i \text{ poised}$	$\mathcal{O}_M \text{ poised} \quad C \text{ poised}$	$\mathcal{M}_{i_0} \text{ live}$
	$\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \text{ poised}$	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) \text{ poised}$	$\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \text{ live}$
LM:COMPOSE:H	LM:COMPOSE:T	BLM: \oplus_P	BLM:1
$\mathcal{O}_M \text{ live}$	$C \text{ live}$	$\text{monitor}(w, \text{record } c) (c, \oplus_P)\text{-blocked}$	$\text{monitor}(w, \text{wait } c \text{ with } k) (c, \text{det})\text{-blocked}$
$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) \text{ live}$	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) \text{ live}$		
BLM:DIST	BLM:COMPOSE:H	BLM:COMPOSE:T	
$\mathcal{M}_{i_0} (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}$	$\mathcal{O}_M (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked} \quad d \notin \text{FV}^R(C)$	$C (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}$	
$\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}$	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}$	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked}$	
CMM:DIST	CMM:COMPOSE:H	CMM:COMPOSE:T	
$\mathcal{M}_{i_0} (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}$	$\mathcal{O}_M (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}$	$C (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}$	
$\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}$	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}$	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-comm}$	
	CMM:COMPOSE:C		
	$\mathcal{O}_M (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked} \quad C (d, \kappa')\text{-poised} \quad \kappa <: \kappa'$		
	$(\mathcal{O}_M \parallel C) (d, \kappa)\text{-poised}$		

The reduction rules of nested multiverse semantics are extended to account for monitor configurations.

$$\begin{array}{l}
\text{(EM:DIST)} \quad \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \mapsto \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{\mathcal{M}'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\}) \\
\quad \text{for some } i_0 \in \mathcal{I} \text{ such that } \mathcal{M}_{i_0} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{M}'_{i_0} \\
\\
\text{(CM:RECORD)} \quad \text{monitor}(w_1, \text{record } d) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_2, d..k : P) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus_P} \text{monitor}(w_1, \text{wait } d \text{ with } k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_2, P) \\
\text{(CM:WAIT)} \quad \text{monitor}(w_1, \text{wait } d \text{ with } k) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_2, \text{close } d) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \text{monitor}(w_1 + w_2, \text{stop } k) \\
\text{(CM:ID)} \quad \text{monitor}(w_1, M\langle d \rangle) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w_2, d \leftrightarrow e) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \text{monitor}(w_1 + w_2, M\langle d \rangle[e/d]) \\
\quad \text{for } M\langle d \rangle \text{ } (d, \kappa)\text{-blocked} \\
\\
\text{(CM:DIST)} \quad \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i_0\}} \# \{\mathcal{M}'_{i_0} : p_{i_0}\}) \\
\quad \text{for some } i_0 \in \mathcal{I} \text{ such that } \mathcal{M}_{i_0} \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}'_{i_0} \\
\text{(CM:SDIST:R)} \quad \text{monitor}(w, M) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}' \\
\quad \text{for } \text{monitor}(\{(\text{monitor}(w, M) \parallel C_i) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}' \\
\text{(CM:SDIST:L)} \quad \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}' \\
\quad \text{for } \text{monitor}(\{(\mathcal{M}_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, w, P)) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}' \\
\text{(CM:BDIST:D)} \quad \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \mathcal{M}'' \\
\quad \text{for } \text{proc}(c, \{(\mathcal{M}_i \parallel C'_j) : p_i \cdot p'_j\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}, j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \text{det}} \mathcal{M}'' \\
\text{(CM:BDIST:R)} \quad \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \&P} \mathcal{M}'' \\
\quad \text{for } \text{monitor}(\{(\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel C'_j) : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \&P} \mathcal{M}'' \\
\text{(CM:BDIST:L)} \quad \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}}) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus_P} \mathcal{M}'' \\
\quad \text{for } \text{monitor}(\{(\mathcal{M}_i \parallel \text{proc}(d, \{C'_j : p'_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{J}})) : p_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}}) \xrightarrow{d, \oplus_P} \mathcal{M}''
\end{array}$$

11.3 Monitor Theorems

Due to the fact that the proofs for monitors follow the exact same reasoning as normal processes (Sections 7 and 8), we only present the results.

PROPOSITION 11.1 (EXTENDED PRESERVATION). *If there is $\Delta \Vdash^w \mathcal{M} \rightsquigarrow A$, and $\mathcal{M} \mapsto \mathcal{M}'$ or $\mathcal{M} \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}'$, then $\Delta \Vdash^w \mathcal{M}' \rightsquigarrow A$*

PROOF. Similar to Theorems 7.11 and 7.12. □

PROPOSITION 11.2. *If \mathcal{M} live, then there exists such \mathcal{M}' such that $\mathcal{M} \mapsto \mathcal{M}'$.*

PROOF. Similar to Lemma 8.2. □

PROPOSITION 11.3. *If \mathcal{M} (d, κ) -comm, then there exists such \mathcal{M}' such that $\mathcal{M} \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}'$.*

PROOF. Similar to Lemma 8.6. □

PROPOSITION 11.4. *If $\cdot \Vdash^w \mathcal{M} \rightsquigarrow A$, then at least one of the following holds:*

- \mathcal{M} live
- \mathcal{M} (d, κ) -comm
- \mathcal{M} poised

PROOF. Similar to Lemma 8.9. □

PROPOSITION 11.5 (EXTENDED GLOBAL PROGRESS). *If $\cdot \Vdash^w \mathcal{M} \rightsquigarrow A$, then one of the following holds:*

- $\mathcal{M} \mapsto \mathcal{M}'$ or $\mathcal{M} \xrightarrow{d, \kappa} \mathcal{M}'$
- \mathcal{M} poised

PROOF. Appeal to Propositions 11.2 to 11.4. □

11.4 Collection

We define a Collect function which computes the distribution of labels in poised (i.e. terminated) monitor configurations.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Collect}[\text{monitor}(w, \text{stop } k)] &:= \{k : 1\} \# \{\ell : 0\}_{\ell \in L \setminus \{k\}} \\ \text{Collect}[\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})] &:= \sum_{i \in I} p_i \cdot \text{Collect}[\mathcal{M}_i] \\ \text{Collect}[(O_M \parallel C)] &:= \text{Collect}[O_M] \end{aligned}$$

Now we begin the proof of probability consistency.

LEMMA 11.6. *If $\Delta \Vdash^w \mathcal{M} \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}$ and \mathcal{M} poised, then $\text{Collect}[\mathcal{M}] = \{\ell : p_\ell\}_{\ell \in L}$.*

PROOF. By induction on the derivation of $\Delta \vdash \mathcal{M} \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}$.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{TM:PROC} \quad \Delta \vdash M \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}}{\Delta \Vdash^w \text{monitor}(w, M) \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}}$$

By inversion on $\text{monitor}(w, M)$ poised we have $M = \text{stop } k$ for some k . By inversion on $\Delta \vdash \text{stop } k \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}$ we have $\Delta = \cdot, p_k = 1$ and $p_l = 0$ for $l \neq k$. Now we have $\text{Collect}[\text{monitor}(w, \text{stop } k)] = \{k : 1\} \# \{\ell : 0\}_{\ell \in L \setminus \{k\}}$ which concludes this case.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{TM:DIST} \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall (i \in I) \quad \Delta_i \Vdash^{w_i} \mathcal{M}_i \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p'_{i,\ell}} : 1\}_{\ell \in L} \\ \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I}^L r_i \cdot \Delta_i = \Delta \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I} r_i \cdot p'_{i,\ell} = p_\ell \quad \cdot ; \top \vDash \sum_{i \in I} r_i * w_i = w \end{array}}{\Delta \Vdash \text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : r_i\}_{i \in I}) \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}}$$

Since $\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})$ poised requires each \mathcal{M}_i to be poised, by induction we know that there is $\text{Collect}[\mathcal{M}_i] = \{\ell : p'_{i,\ell}\}_{\ell \in L}$.

By definition, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Collect}[\text{monitor}(\{\mathcal{M}_i : p_i\}_{i \in I})] &= \sum_{i \in I} r_i \cdot \{\ell : p'_{i,\ell}\}_{\ell \in L} \\ &= \{\ell : \sum_{i \in I} r_i \cdot p'_{i,\ell}\}_{\ell \in L} \\ &= \{\ell : p_\ell\}_{\ell \in L} \end{aligned}$$

which concludes this case.

Case:

$$\frac{\text{TM:COMPOSE} \quad \Delta_1, \Delta \Vdash^{w_1} O_M \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L} \quad \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_2} C :: \Delta}{\Delta_1, \Delta_2 \Vdash^{w_1+w_2} (O_M \parallel C) \rightsquigarrow \oplus_P \{\ell^{p_\ell} : 1\}_{\ell \in L}}$$

This case is immediately proven by appealing to induction hypothesis. □

THEOREM 11.7 (CONSISTENCY). *If $\cdot \Vdash^w C :: (c : \oplus_P \{l^{p_l} : A\}_{l \in L})$ and C evaluates to a poised configuration C' , the monitored distribution of messages on c in C' is consistent with $\oplus_P \{l^{p_l} : A\}_{l \in L}$.*

PROOF. Appeal to Propositions 11.1 and 11.5 and lemma 11.6. □

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